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**CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MECHANISMS OF
ACTION OF ANTICANCER AGENTS *IN VITRO* AND
MONITORING THEIR EFFECTS *IN VIVO***

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An education isn't how much you have committed to memory, or even how much you know. It's being able to differentiate between what you do know and what you don't.

Anatole France (1844 - 1924)

*To my son **Özlen**,
my **Parents & Sisters***

ABSTRACT

Chemotherapeutic drug resistance is a major clinical problem and cause for failure in the therapy of human cancer. Mutations in apoptotic programs may promote tumour progression and reduce the efficacy of cancer therapy. Mutations within the p53 gene are found in about half of all human cancers and loss of p53 function correlates with multi-drug resistance in many tumour types. Anti-cancer therapy is generally believed to induce tumour apoptosis and apoptosis is an attractive clinical endpoint for evaluation of treatment efficiency. The aims of this thesis were to identify agents that induce p53-independent apoptosis and to characterize the mechanisms of action such drugs and to develop a new approach for monitor treatment responses.

We have developed a simple assay system for detection of apoptosis and also necrosis both in vivo and in vitro. The apoptosis assay is based on measurement of caspase-cleaved cytokeratin-18 and detected by the monoclonal antibody M30. The M30-ELISA is a novel high-throughput assay for screening and characterization of compounds that induce apoptosis. Another assay, the M65-ELISA, was also developed that measures full-length soluble CK18 and CK18 COOH terminal fragments. Our results showed large differences in the ratios of caspase-cleaved to total CK18 in the sera of different patients. Our results suggest that apoptosis is not the main mechanisms of spontaneous or therapy associated cell death in the many tumours

We identified agents that induce p53-independent apoptosis and characterized their mechanisms of action by screening a drug library from the National Cancer Institute (NCI). The result shows that a large number of potential anti-cancer drugs induce p53-independent apoptosis and lysosomal membrane potential (LMP) is a mediator of many such responses. We identified two different mechanisms of LMP induction. One group of compounds induce reactive oxygen species (ROS) whereas the second group did not. Evidence suggesting a Bax-regulated pathway of LMP induction was obtained.

These results establish a unique role of LMP in the pathways of cell death and may have implications for cancer chemoprevention strategies. Enhancing the lysosomal cell death pathway may be a therapeutic strategy to overcome the chemoresistance. Due to the high frequency of p53 mutations in human cancer cells, the demonstration that LMP is potentially a common mechanism of action of p53-independent drugs and the association of ROS with induction of LMP are interesting in terms of future drug development.

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

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- I. Biven K, **Erdal H**, Hagg M, Ueno T, Zhou R, Lynch M, Rowley B, Wood J, Zhang C, Toi M, Shoshan MC, Linder S.
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Expression of DNA-PKcs and Ku86, but not Ku70, differs between lymphoid malignancies. *Exp Mol Pathol*. 2004 Aug;77(1):1-6.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	1
1.1	CELL DEATH	1
1.1.1	<i>Historical perspective of cell death.....</i>	<i>1</i>
1.1.2	<i>Apoptosis.....</i>	<i>1</i>
1.1.3	<i>Necrosis.....</i>	<i>1</i>
1.2	FACTORS WHICH DETERMINE WHETHER THE CELL ENGAGES IN APOPTOSIS OR NECROSIS	2
1.3	THE MAJOR APOPTOTIC PATHWAYS	3
1.3.1	<i>The extrinsic pathway.....</i>	<i>3</i>
1.3.2	<i>The intrinsic pathway.....</i>	<i>4</i>
1.4	THE BCL-2 FAMILY	6
1.4.1	<i>Anti-apoptotic proteins.....</i>	<i>6</i>
1.4.2	<i>Pro-apoptotic proteins.....</i>	<i>6</i>
1.5	ROLE OF P53 IN REGULATION OF APOPTOSIS.....	8
1.6	STRESS RESPONSES AND ANTI-CANCER DRUGS	9
1.6.1	<i>Stress responses.....</i>	<i>9</i>
1.6.2	<i>Sphingolipids.....</i>	<i>9</i>
1.6.3	<i>The role of Reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cell death.....</i>	<i>9</i>
1.6.4	<i>Cancer chemotherapy.....</i>	<i>11</i>
1.6.5	<i>Anti-cancer drugs.....</i>	<i>11</i>
1.7	THE INVOLVEMENT OF CYTOKERATIN-18 IN CELL DEATH.....	12
1.8	INVOLVEMENT OF CELL ORGANELLES IN APOPTOSIS	14
1.8.1	<i>The role of mitochondria in the apoptotic response.....</i>	<i>14</i>
1.8.2	<i>Apoptosis regulation at the endoplasmic reticulum.....</i>	<i>15</i>
1.8.3	<i>The involvement of nucleus in apoptosis.....</i>	<i>16</i>
1.9	LYSOSOMAL INVOLVEMENT IN APOPTOSIS	17
1.9.1	<i>Mechanisms of lysosomal membrane permeabilization.....</i>	<i>19</i>
1.9.2	<i>Lysosomes in the apoptosis pathway.....</i>	<i>19</i>
2	THE PRESENT STUDY	22
2.1	AIM(S)	22
2.2	RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.....	23
2.2.1	<i>Paper I and Paper II.....</i>	<i>23</i>
2.2.2	<i>Paper III and Paper IV.....</i>	<i>25</i>
3	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	31
4	REFERENCES	33

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGS3	G-protein-signaling-3
AIF	Apoptosis inducing factor
ANT	Adenine nucleotide translocator
AP-1	Activator protein-1
Apaf-1	Apoptosis protease-activator factor-1
ASK	Apoptosis Stimulating kinase
A-SMase	Acid SMase
ATF-2	Activating transcription factor-2
ATM	Ataxia telangiectasia mutated
ATR	ATM and Rad3-related
Bcl-2	B cell lymphoma-2
BH	Bcl-2 homology
CAD	Caspase-activated Dnase
CK	Cytokeratins
DED	Death effector domain
DFO	Iron chelator desferoxamine
DISK	Death-inducing signalling complex
DNA-PK	DNA-dependent protein kinase
ER	Endoplasmic reticulum
ERK	Extracellular signal regulated kinase
FADD	Fas-associated death domain
FAN	Factor associated with neutral sphingomyelinase activation
FFA	Free fatty acid
GSH	Glutathione
GSH	Glutathione
H ₂ O ₂	Hydrogen Peroxide
IAP	Inhibitor of apoptosis protein
ICAD	Initiator of CAD
IM	Inner membrane
JNK/SPAK	c-jun NH ₂ -terminal protein kinase/stress activated protein kinase
LMP	Lysosomal membrane permeabilization

MAPK	Mitogen-activated protein kinase
MEF	Mouse embryo fibroblasts
MIA	Microtubule interactive agent
MMP	Mitochondrial membrane permeabilization
MPT	Mitochondrial Permeability Transition
NAC	N-acetyl cysteine
NCI	National Cancer Institute
NF- κ B	Nuclear factor-kappa B
N-SMase	Neutral magnesium-dependent SMase
PARP	Poly (ADP-Ribose) polymerase
PCD	Programmed cell death
PERK	PKR-like ER kinase
PI3-K	Phosphatidyl inositol-3 kinase
PKR	RNA-activated protein kinase
PLA2	Phospholipase A2
PS	Phosphotidyl serine
PSA	Prostate-specific antigen
PTP	Permeability transition pore
PTPC	PTP complex
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RTK	Receptor tyrosine kinase
S1P	Sphingosine-1-phosphate
SERCA	Sarcoplasmic/endoplasmic Ca ²⁺ -ATP transporter
SK1	Sphingosine kinase isoform
SM	Sphingomyelin
Spi2A	Serine protease inhibitor 2A
tBid	Truncated Bid
TNF	Tumour necrosis factor
TNFR1	Tumour necrosis factor receptor-1
TPA	Tissue polypeptide antigen
TPS	Tissue-polypeptide-specific antigen
TRAIL	TNF-related apoptosis inducing ligand
UPR	Unfolded protein kinase
VDAC	Voltage dependent anion channel

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 CELL DEATH

Cell death is a critical process in development and homeostasis of normal organisms. All cells are equipped with a genetic program for self-destruction that plays important roles in balancing cell proliferation with cell death and many other physiological processes. Apoptosis is a key regulator of tissue homeostasis, which critically depends on the equilibrium of cells maintain the correct number. Apoptosis and necrosis are two forms of cell death, with well defined morphological and biochemical differences. Apoptosis occurs under normal physiological conditions and is an active process requiring energy. Biochemical hallmarks of apoptosis such as activation of caspases are usually absent in necrotic cells (Evan and Dail 1974; Desagher and Martinou 2000).

1.1.1 *Historical perspective of cell death*

The naturally occurring turnover of cells in the body is referred to as “programmed cell death” (also known as "apoptosis"). That cell death occurs in a predictable “programmed” form in physiological conditions was first recognized in the neuronal system of developing toad embryos and the phrase “programmed cell death” (PCD) used in 1965 to describe cell death in insect metamorphosis (Lockshin and Williams 1965). Kerr and colleagues coined a new term “apoptosis” for cell death with distinct morphology - whether it occurs in response to physiologic or pathologic stimuli (Kerr, Wyllie et al. 1972) .

1.1.2 *Apoptosis*

The cell and molecular biology of apoptosis has been studied in great detail in a number of invertebrate and vertebrate model systems. A genetic understanding of cell death has primarily come from study of *C elegans* (Ellis and Horvitz 1986). Apoptosis is responsible for solitary cell death necessary for the maintenance of a correct cell number in various tissues, in embryogenesis, in tissue disorders and tissue atrophy. Characteristics of apoptosis include cell shrinkage, activation of caspases, DNA cleavage, chromatin condensation, and nuclear fragmentation. During apoptosis, activation of endonucleases causes double-strand breaks in DNA between nucleosomes leading to that DNA is fragmented into multiples of 200 base pair pieces. When the DNA of apoptotic cells is electrophoresed, a characteristic ladder pattern is found (Wyllie, Kerr et al. 1980; Wyllie 1985).

1.1.3 *Necrosis*

Necrotic cell death is an unregulated process resulting from severe damage, such as ATP depletion, hypoxia, various toxins and hyperthermia and characterized by cell swelling, lysis, and the release of intracellular contents associated with pathological tissue injury (Wyllie, Kerr et al. 1980). Necrosis is associated with release of lysosomal proteases, which causes proteolysis of nuclear histones, leaving “naked” stretches of

DNA not protected by histones. Electrophoresis of DNA from necrotic cells results in a smear pattern (Fadeel, Zhivotovsky et al. 1999). In addition, necrotic cells enhance pro-inflammatory responses of activated macrophages, whereas apoptotic cells profoundly inhibit these (Cocco and Ucker 2001).

1.2 FACTORS WHICH DETERMINE WHETHER THE CELL ENGAGES IN APOPTOSIS OR NECROSIS

Mitochondria constitute an important component of the cell death machinery. The mitochondrial permeability transition (MPT) is a common pathway leading to both necrotic and apoptotic cell death (Kim, Qian et al. 2003). Signals that trigger or switch cell death pathways are ATP, reactive oxygen species (ROS) and apoptotic/necrotic factors.

Apoptosis is an energy dependent process, and decrement of ATP levels may cause the a shift from apoptosis to necrosis (Eguchi, Shimizu et al. 1997). Oxygen radicals are created under different physiological and toxic conditions may induce cell death by selectively altering the structure and the function of the plasma membrane. Free radicals interact with lipids, proteins and other cellular constituents, leading to cell death (Halliwell 2000). Cell death induced by free radicals may have characteristics of apoptosis or necrosis (Kane, Sarafian et al. 1993). Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) causes apoptosis or necrosis, depending on the intracellular concentrations (Troyano, Sancho et al. 2003) and the depletion of intracellular glutathione (GSH) diverts the mode of death from apoptosis to necrosis in drug treated cells (Troyano, Fernandez et al. 2001).

Different intercellular mediators and their receptors, TNF (tumour necrosis factor), FAS (also known as CD95 or Apo-1), and TRAIL (TNF-related apoptosis inducing ligand) can activate both apoptosis and necrosis. The mechanisms of TNF- α - induced necrosis have been studied in detail, and the induction of ROS has been found to be a key factor (Lin, Choksi et al. 2004).

The enzyme poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) is a nuclear enzyme involved in DNA repair and activated by DNA damage (Lazebnik, Kaufmann et al. 1994). Strong activation of PARP activity can cause depletion of NAD⁺, and consequently ATP depletion, and leading to a shift from apoptosis to necrosis (Affar el, Shah et al. 2002).

1.3 THE MAJOR APOPTOTIC PATHWAYS

Apoptosis is mediated by a group of specific family of cysteine proteases, the caspases. These enzymes are typically activated in the early stages of apoptosis by processing from its inactive precursor (zymogen) and are involved in both initiation and execution of apoptosis (Thornberry and Lazebnik 1998).

Caspases

Caspases can be found in humans all the way down to insects, nematodes and hydra. The involvement of caspases in apoptosis was discovered in *C elegans*. To date, at least 14 mammalian caspases have been identified. In mammals caspases have been subdivided into two classes: the initiator caspases (caspase -1, -2, -4, -5, -8, -9, -10 and -12) and the effector caspases (caspases-3, -6, -7, -11 and -13).

Fully active caspases are tetramers consisting of two large subunits (~20kDa) and two small subunits (~10kDa). The inhibitory pro-domain must then be cleaved and removed (Thornberry and Lazebnik 1998). The active heterotetramer is formed with two cysteinyl active sites, which appear to operate independently. The initiator caspases contain a long prodomain at the N-terminus whereas effector caspases contain a short prodomain.

The activation of initiator caspases is regulated by protein-protein interactions in cells and these processes in turn trigger a cascade of downstream caspase activation. The substrates of effector caspases, primarily caspase-3 and -7, are either signalling or structure proteins. Cleavage of these substrates results in the morphological and functional changes associated with apoptosis. The result of morphological changes is cell shrinkage, chromatin condensation, DNA fragmentation and plasma membrane blebbing (Nicholson and Thornberry 1997; Thornberry and Lazebnik 1998). The active caspase-3 cleaves the inhibitory subunit of ICAD, thus releases CAD, which is involved in cleavage of the DNA. Caspase activity leads also to the externalisation of phosphatidyl-serine, a phospholipid normally found in the inner leaflet of the plasma membrane. Phagocytes bind to these phospholipids. Caspases also induce cytoskeletal reorganisation, and disintegration of the cell into apoptotic bodies. Two different pathways, the so-called extrinsic and intrinsic pathways, mediate the activation of caspases.

1.3.1 *The extrinsic pathway*

This pathway is activated by death receptors, which are cell surface receptors that transmit apoptosis signals initiated by specific ligands. They play an important role in apoptosis and can activate a caspase cascade within seconds of ligand binding.

The best characterised of the death receptors are CD95 (also known as Apo-1 or Fas), TNFR1 (tumour necrosis factor receptor-1) and the TRAIL (TNF-related apoptosis inducing ligand) receptors DR4 and DR5. In a number of ways, TRAIL is similar in action to CD95 and contains death domains in its intracellular domain. Association between ligands and their receptors can lead to receptor trimerisation and recruitment of adaptor proteins to the cytoplasmic death domain (DD). This allows adapter proteins

FADD (CD95-associated death domain) or TRADD (TNFR and TRAIL-R associated death domain) to associate with these receptors through an interaction between homologous death-domains. The death effector domain allows binding of pro-caspase 8 to the CD95/FADD or TNFR/TRADD complex. Upon recruitment by FADD/TRADD, caspase-8 is immediately cleaved to produce an active form. This then triggers activation of execution caspases such as caspase 9. The complex of proteins CD95/FADD or TNFR/TRADD and pro-caspase-8 is also known as DISC or Death Inducing Signaling Complex (Budihardjo, Oliver et al. 1999; Igney and Krammer 2002).

There are two pathways downstream of caspase-8 that can activate downstream caspases directly and/or through proapoptotic protein Bid and mitochondria (Scaffidi, Fulda et al. 1998). In type I cells, such as thymocytes and fibroblasts, caspase-8 directly activates caspase-3. In type II cells such as hepatocytes, caspase-8 cleaves Bid, a member of the Bcl-2 family. Caspase-8 is the key initiator caspase in the extrinsic pathway of apoptosis and Bid is a link between the extrinsic and intrinsic apoptotic pathways.

1.3.2 *The intrinsic pathway*

The intrinsic pathway is mainly mediated by mitochondria and is triggered by various forms of extracellular and intracellular stress, such as hypoxia, DNA damage and oncogene induction. Mitochondria have a central role in apoptosis, and an increase in mitochondrial membrane permeability is commonly observed (Martinou and Green 2001). The release of the cytochrome c is resulting in the formation of the apoptosome and activation of procaspase-9. The apoptosome is a large protein complex that contains cytochrome c, apoptotic protease activating factor 1 (Apaf-1) and caspase-9. Activated caspase-9 cleaves and activates procaspase-7 and procaspase-3, which initiate the process of apoptosis (Slee, Harte et al. 1999). The downstream cascade of caspase activation is irreversible (Goldstein, Waterhouse et al. 2000).

Mitochondrial membrane permeabilization leads to the release of other factors than cytochrome c, including apoptosis-inducing factor (AIF), Endonuclease G, Smac/DIABLO and Omi/HtrA2 from the intermembrane space. Smac/Diablo and HtrA2/Omi repress inhibitors of caspase-9, the inhibitor of apoptosis proteins (IAPs) (Du, Fang et al. 2000; Verhagen, Ekert et al. 2000; Martins, Iaccarino et al. 2002). Endonuclease G and AIF are proposed to translocate from the intermembrane space to the nucleus where they are involved in DNA fragmentation and chromatin condensation and might also induce cell death independently of caspase activation (Susin, Daugas et al. 2000; Li, Luo et al. 2001).

Figure 1. Two major apoptotic pathways in mammalian cells

1.4 THE BCL-2 FAMILY

The Bcl-2 proteins consist of a protein family of at least 25 members. These proteins are known to affect mitochondrial function and regulate the release of activating factors of apoptosis from mitochondria (Tsujimoto and Shimizu 2000). Bcl-2 family proteins are divided into two classes: those that inhibit apoptosis and those that promote apoptosis. They are related through their conservation of helical sequences known as Bcl-2 homology (BH) domains and each Bcl-2 family member contain at least one of these four BH-domains, BH1-BH4 (Scorrano and Korsmeyer 2003). Bcl-2 family proteins can interact with each other, forming homodimers, heterodimers and oligodimers.

1.4.1 *Anti-apoptotic proteins*

The anti-apoptotic proteins, Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL, Bcl-w, Mcl-1, Bfl-1 contain all four BH domains, and promote cell survival by binding to pro-apoptotic Bcl-2 proteins and inhibiting their function. Bcl-xL and Bcl-w protect cells from UV- and γ -irradiation, cytotoxic and anticancer agents. Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL exist in the outer mitochondrial membrane, endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and the nuclear membranes (Krajewski, Tanaka et al. 1993; Lithgow, van Driel et al. 1994). The hydrophobic sequence in C-terminus of Bcl-2 proteins are important for targeting to the intracellular membranes. Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL have been suggested to act as barriers to membrane permeabilization by physically or functionally interacting with voltage-dependent anion channel (VDAC), by neutralizing adenine nucleotide translocator (ANT) channel activity, or a combination of all of these (Martinou and Green 2001). Bcl-xL, Bcl-2 and Bax have all been shown to form ion channels in synthetic lipid membranes (Tsujimoto 2002). Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL bind and inhibit Bid or tBid to interact with and inducing the oligomerization of Bax and Bak (Cheng, Wei et al. 2001).

1.4.2 *Pro-apoptotic proteins*

The pro-apoptotic Bcl-2 proteins can be divided into two classes. The multi-domain protein Bax subclass (Bax, Bak and Bok) possess sequence homology for the BH1, BH2, and BH3 region (Muchmore, Sattler et al. 1996). These proteins can promote apoptosis via their interaction with the mitochondrial membrane leading to release of cytochrome c and activation of caspases. The second subclass (Bik, Bim, Blk, Bid, Bad, Hrk, Puma and Noxa) have strong homology only in the BH3 region (Puthalakath and Strasser 2002).

Bax and Bak

Bax and Bak have important roles in the intrinsic pathway of cell death at both the mitochondria and ER. Bak exists predominantly in mitochondria and ER membranes whereas Bax is found mainly in the cytosol. The gene encoding Bax is a transcriptional target of p53 in humans (Miyashita and Reed 1995). In response to death stimuli activated Bax and Bak undergo homo-oligomerization that results in the permeabilization of the outer mitochondrial membrane and the release of cytochrome c (Nechushtan, Smith et al. 1999). Bax and Bak can also operate at the ER to control

calcium levels. Calpain has been shown to cleave Bax both *in vitro* and in intact cells (Wood and Newcomb 1999). Several studies have been reported that truncated Bax proteins (p18 and p29) cleaved by calpain were more apoptotic than full length Bax (Wood and Newcomb 1999; Gao and Dou 2000; Toyota, Yanase et al. 2003).

Mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEF) lacking both Bax and Bak (Bax^{-/-}Bak^{-/-}) are resistant to different form of apoptotic stimuli including t-Bid, Bim, Bad, Noxa, staurosporine, ultraviolet radiation, growth factor deprivation, etoposide, oxygen deprivation, thapsigargin and tunicamycin (Cheng, Wei et al. 2001; Wei, Zong et al. 2001; Zong, Lindsten et al. 2001; Lee, McClintock et al. 2002).

Figure 2: The Bcl-2 family of proteins

BH3-only proteins

Different mechanisms are involved in translocation of BH3-only proapoptotic proteins from the cytosol to the mitochondria. Bad is found in the cytosol and its translocalization to the mitochondria is regulated by phosphorylation and binding to 14-3-3 scaffold proteins (Zha, Harada et al. 1996). Bim and Bmf are bound to the cytoskeleton that keeps them in an inactive form (Coults, Pellegrini et al. 2003).

In healthy cells Bid is cytosolic. Activated caspase-8 cleaves the amino portion of Bid to form a truncated (t-Bid) (Luo, Budihardjo et al. 1998). Bid is also cleaved by granzyme B (Atkinson, Barry et al. 1998), calpain (Mandic, Viktorsson et al. 2002) and cathepsins (B,H,L and S) (Cirman, Oresic et al. 2004). Caspases and granzyme B have stricter substrate specificity than the cathepsins (Harris, Backes et al. 2000). However, tBid can be further posttranslationally modified by myristylation (Zha, Weiler et al. 2000). Bad, Bim, and Noxa can induce apoptosis via an interaction with either Bax or Bak and/or by generating stable complexes with anti-apoptotic Bcl-2/Bcl-xL (Adams and Cory 2001; Cheng, Wei et al. 2001). The genes encoding the BH3-only proteins Puma and Noxa are transcriptionally transactivated by p53 (Oda, Ohki et al. 2000; Nakano and Vousden 2001).

1.5 ROLE OF P53 IN REGULATION OF APOPTOSIS

p53 is the mostly studied tumour suppressor protein and discovered in 1979 due to its interaction with SV40 T antigen (Lane 1992). p53 is an important inhibitor of tumour development and mutated in up to 50% of human tumors (Vogelstein, Lane et al. 2000). The nuclear protein p53 is also a transcription factor that has five conserved domains designated boxes I-V and four main functional domains (el-Deiry, Kern et al. 1992).

p53 is activated by external and internal cellular stress such as hypoxia, DNA-damage, oncogene activation and viral infection that promotes its nuclear accumulation in an active form. Activated p53 protein arrests the cell cycle or leads to apoptosis. The ATM (ataxia telangiectasia mutated) and ATR (ATM and Rad3-related) kinases are activated in response to DNA double strand breaks and play key roles in activation of p53 (Abraham 2001). p53 is negative regulated by Mdm2, which is a p53-inducible E3 ubiquitin ligase responsible for degradation of p53. There are two p53 homologues, p63 and p73, linked to apoptosis, which share key functional domain with p53 (Melino, De Laurenzi et al. 2002).

p53 is involved in apoptosis through its transcriptional regulatory functions, in addition to less known transcription-independent activities (Vousden and Lu 2002). p53 can induce the expression of Bax, Noxa and Puma, which translocate from the cytosol to the outer mitochondrial membrane (Hwang, Bunz et al. 2001; Vousden and Lu 2002). p53 also induces Apaf-1 expression (MacLachlan and El-Deiry 2002; Rozenfeld-Granot, Krishnamurthy et al. 2002).

p53 is also involved in the expression of mitochondrial enzymes that locally generate ROS. Recent studies have demonstrated that a fraction of stress-activated p53 is also translocated to the mitochondria after an apoptotic stimulus and may act directly upstream of Bak (Marchenko, Zaika et al. 2000).

1.6 STRESS RESPONSES AND ANTI-CANCER DRUGS

All cells sense and respond to changes in their environment, such as variations in pH, temperature and osmolarity, as well as exposure to UV irradiation and a range of potentially toxic compounds. These types of changes have effects on cellular functions, which result in proliferation, migration, differentiation or cell death.

1.6.1 Stress responses

Kinase mediated signaling pathways play prominent roles in the control of cell proliferation, stress response, differentiation and apoptosis. The mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) group of serine/threonine protein kinases is activated by a protein kinase cascade mechanism through phosphorylation in response to many extracellular stimuli (Schaeffer and Weber 1999). These protein kinases include the extracellular signal-regulated protein kinases (ERKs) and stress-activated protein kinases (SAPK), the c-Jun N-terminal kinases (JNKs), and the p38 MAPK (Gupta, Campbell et al. 1995; Schaeffer and Weber 1999).

The ERK cascade plays a key role in the conduction of many proliferative and differentiative signals involved in normal development and tumorigenesis. The SAPK members consist of the JNK and p38 MAP kinases and are activated by multiple alternative protein kinases (Davis 2000). This enables the precise control of SAPK activity *in vivo* following exposure of cells to cytokines, growth factors, and various forms of stress (Davis 2000). The *Jnk1*, *Jnk2* and *Jnk3* genes encode the JNK protein kinases. The *Jnk1* and *Jnk2* genes express ubiquitously whereas expression of *Jnk3* gene is limited to brain, heart, and testis. Mouse fibroblast deficient with regard to *Jnk1* and *Jnk2* are resistant to various forms of apoptotic stimuli (Tournier, Hess et al. 2000).

1.6.2 Sphingolipids

The family of sphingolipids are included in the membrane lipids and their metabolites, including ceramide, sphingosine and sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P) are recognized as second messengers playing essential roles in cell growth, survival and death (Hannun, Luberto et al. 2001).

Membrane neutral magnesium-dependent SMase (N-SMase) and acid SMase (A-SMase) are activated by diverse stress stimuli resulting in increased ceramide levels (Mathias, Pena et al. 1998). Ceramide is specially involved in the regulation of cancer-cell growth, differentiation, senescence and apoptosis (Hannun, Luberto et al. 2001).

1.6.3 The role of Reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cell death

ROS are oxygen containing chemical species with reactive chemical properties such as superoxide and hydroxyl radicals (which contain unpaired electrons) and also hydrogen peroxide (non-radical molecules). ROS can be formed by both exogenous and endogenous sources in cells. ROS may damage various cellular components including DNA, protein, and lipid membranes of nuclei, mitochondria, golgi and lysosomes.

Low levels of ROS regulate cellular signalling and play an important role in normal cell proliferation. One of the first observations of the cellular response to oxygen-induced

cytotoxicity was decreased proliferation in HeLa cells (Rueckert and Mueller 1960). ROS generation during mitogenic stimulation may inhibit phosphatases and tyrosine phosphatases, facilitating the activation of associated receptor tyrosine kinases (Kamata and Hirata 1999). Endogenously produced ROS via NADPH oxidases, stimulated by Rac, are important mediators of actin cytoskeleton remodeling (Moldovan, Irani et al. 1999).

ROS levels are increased in cells exposed to various stress agents, including anticancer drugs (Feinendegen 2002), and they promote apoptosis by stimulating pro-apoptotic signalling molecules. ROS are also involved in hypoxia-induced apoptosis through the BH3-only protein and also the activation of the redox sensitive of c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK/SAPK) and p38 mitogen-activated protein (MAP) kinase pathways (De Zutter and Davis 2001).

Increase in oxidative stress can induce various biological responses, ranging from a transient growth arrest and adaptation, increase in cellular proliferation, permanent growth arrest (senescence), apoptosis and necrosis (Davies 1999). The actual outcomes are likely to be dependent on the cellular genetic background, the specific types of the ROS involved, and the levels and duration of the oxidative stress. Oxidative stress can also induce DNA damage that leads to genomic instability, which may contribute to cancer progression (Jackson and Loeb 2001) and also tumour initiation.

The degree of oxidative stress in a cell depends on the balance between the ROS generation and elimination processes. A variety of cellular antioxidants have been identified which specifically eliminate ROS. These include superoxide dismutases, catalases, glutathione, alpha-tocopherol, vitamins A and C, and melanin. However, antioxidants are not able to fully protect DNA from oxidative stress and various lesions in DNA such as base modifications, degradation products of deoxyribose, and strand breaks are known to occur. Therefore, the second line of defense against oxidative stress involves DNA repair. The cellular defense mechanisms against ROS include redox buffering systems and various antioxidant enzymes. The glutathione and thioredoxin systems are the main cellular factors responsible for maintaining intracellular proteins in a reduced state (Schafer and Buettner 2001).

Enzymes containing metals such as cytochrome c, cytochrome c oxidase, glutathione peroxidase, and catalases can be damaged by oxidation. Oxidative-stress as well as application of H₂O₂ induces specific oxidation of several essential ER proteins including Grp78, Grp94, and calnexin (van der Vlies, Woudenberg et al. 2003). Oxidatively modified proteins can be recognized by proteases such as Ca²⁺-dependent protease, acid protease (cathepsin B), which are indirectly involved in cell death pathways. Lysosomes and peroxisomes are involved mostly in catabolic processes. The enzymatic activities accommodated by these organelles depend on pH and/or the redox environment, and are mostly oxidative reactions. The result of lysosomal and peroxisomal functioning includes damaging chemical species, either directly (H₂O₂) or indirectly (iron stores and lipofuscin). A consequence of oxidative stress in lysosomes is destabilization of their membranes, due to peroxidation (Nilsson, Ghassemifar et al. 1997). Mitochondria are continually exposed to ROS leading to peroxidation of membrane lipids, cleavage of mitochondrial DNA and impairment of ATP generation.

1.6.4 Cancer chemotherapy

There are three main approaches to treating established cancer: surgical excision, irradiation and chemotherapy. The role of each of these depends on the type of tumour and the stage of its development. Chemotherapy is the treatment of cancer with drugs that can damage cancer cells. These drugs often are called "anticancer" drugs

1.6.5 Anti-cancer drugs

Anti-cancer agents can be divided into different main categories based on their mode of action. There are only few biochemical differences between cancer cells and normal cells and for this reason the efficacy of many anti-cancer drugs is limited by their toxicity to normal rapidly growing cells. Some of the currently used anticancer drugs are listed below.

Microtubule interactive agents (MIAs)

Microtubules are protein polymers that are responsible for various aspects of cellular shape and movement. The major component of microtubules is tubulin, a protein containing two nonidentical subunits (alpha and beta). MIAs act by affecting the equilibrium between free tubulin dimers and assembled polymers.

Vinca alkaloids are large molecules produced by the leaves of the periwinkle plant. There are slight structural differences between the different vinca alkaloids, which lead to significant differences in therapeutic uses and toxicity. These agents act by binding to tubulin and inhibit its polymerisation in cells undergoing mitosis, leading to arrest at metaphase.

Taxanes are derivatives of yew tree bark and act on microtubules, stabilising them in a polymerised state. Taxanes have significant activity against ovarian cancer, breast cancer and head and neck carcinoma. Resistance to vinca alkaloids and taxanes is due primarily to decreased drug accumulation and results from overexpression of the P-glycoprotein.

Topoisomerase inhibitors

Etoposide is derived from mandrake root and inhibits DNA synthesis by inhibiting topoisomerase II. Etoposide has an important role in the treatment of small cell lung carcinomas where it is often combined with cisplatin. Doxorubicin is an anthracycline antibiotic that inhibits DNA and RNA synthesis. The DNA effect is mainly due to interference with topoisomerase II action. The camptotecins are a new class of chemotherapeutic agents with a novel mechanism of action targeting the nuclear enzyme topoisomerase I.

DNA interacting agents

The alkylating agents form strong electrophiles through the formation of carbonium ion intermediates. This results in the formation of covalent linkages by alkylation of various nucleophilic moieties. The chemotherapeutic and cytotoxic effects are directly related to the alkylation of DNA. The nucleophilic groups of proteins, RNA and many other molecules can also be subject to attack by the alkylating agents although the exact

result of these interactions is not known. The alkylating agents are generally considered to be cell cycle-phase nonspecific. They also are known to be most cytotoxic to rapidly proliferating cells. The main alkylating agents are nitrogen mustards, busulphan and nitrosoureas.

Cisplatin is one of a number of platinum complexes with anti-tumour activity. The platinum compounds are DNA cross-linking agents similar to but not identical to the alkylating agents. The types of cross-linking with DNA may differ between the platinum compounds and the typical alkylating agents. Cisplatin is one of the most frequently used anticancer drugs.

The bleomycins are a group of antitumor agents isolated from *Streptomyces vericillus*. Bleomycin is a metal binding water-soluble glycopeptide antibiotic. Bleomycin has been found to profoundly inhibit DNA synthesis while RNA and protein synthesis are much less affected.

Antimetabolites

Antimetabolites block-cellular metabolic pathways involved in DNA synthesis. This class includes folate antagonists, pyrimidine analogues and purine analogues.

Folate antagonists: the main folate antagonist is methotrexate. Methotrexate inhibits dihydrofolate reductase, preventing generation of tetrahydrofolate. This results in interference with thymidylate synthesis. Pyrimidine analogues: fluorouracil interferes with thymidylate synthesis and therefore with synthesis of DNA. Purine analogues: mercaptopurine is converted into a nucleotide that cannot be used for RNA or DNA synthesis.

Endocrine therapy

Tamoxifen is a competitive inhibitor of estradiol binding to the estrogen receptor. It acts as a complete antagonist in some systems and as an antagonist with partial agonist activity in other systems. Tamoxifen is used in the treatment of metastatic breast cancer. A number of antiandrogens, steroidal and non-steroidal, are used for treatment of prostate cancer patients.

1.7 THE INVOLVEMENT OF CYTOKERATIN-18 IN CELL DEATH

Apoptosis is characterized by a distinct series of morphological and biochemical changes. Many of the proteolytic cleavages occurring during apoptosis are mediated by caspases that selectively cleave several substrates during apoptosis. Caspases selectively cleave a restricted set of target proteins, usually at one, or at most a few positions in the primary sequence (always after an aspartate residue). Several important caspase substrates have been identified and these known substrates are categorized into a few functional groups including proteins involved in the cytoplasm and cell nucleus, signal transduction and transcription regulatory proteins, cell cycle controlling components and proteins involved in DNA replication and repair (Kroemer, Petit et al. 1995). Cytokeratins (CKs) are among these substrates. CKs are epithelial-specific intermediate filament proteins. At least 30 different CK-proteins have been identified in epithelial tissues and carcinomas and these are grouped into two main types based on

sequence homology: type I, which are cytokeratins 9–20 (40–56 kDa, acidic proteins) and type II, which are cytokeratins 1–8 (53–68 kDa, neutral to basic protein components) (Fuchs and Weber 1994). Cytokeratins are insoluble cytoskeleton filaments that can be detected in the circulation of patients either as partially degraded single protein fragments or larger polymeric protein complexes (Rydlander, Ziegler et al. 1996). Serum CK has been extensively used as tumour markers for monitoring patients with epithelial cell carcinomas (Stigbrand 2001). Several assays have been available for measurements of cytokeratins from tumor samples. TPA (tissue polypeptide antigen) detects cytokeratins 8, 18, and 19 (Weber, Osborn et al. 1984), CYFRA 21-1 detects CK19 (Stieber, Dienemann et al. 1993; Rastel, Ramaioli et al. 1994) and TPS (tissue-polypeptide-specific antigen) detect C-terminal epitope on CK18 (Rydlander, Ziegler et al. 1996).

1.8 INVOLVEMENT OF CELL ORGANELLES IN APOPTOSIS

Apoptosis is induced by various extracellular and intracellular stresses acting on specific organelles including mitochondria, the endoplasmic reticulum, nuclei or lysosomes and characterized by common morphological and biochemical alterations (Ferri and Kroemer 2001).

1.8.1 The role of mitochondria in the apoptotic response

The mitochondrial release of pro-apoptotic factors is not completely understood. In many apoptosis scenarios, the mitochondrial inner electrical transmembrane potential collapses, indicating the opening of large conductance channels through the inner membrane. In contrast, certain stimuli can induce rupture of the outer membrane of mitochondria and release of caspase-activation proteins. The lipid composition of the inner membrane (IM) of mitochondria is very different than the other intracellular membranes. The IM is the only eukaryotic membrane that contains cardiolipin. IM contains a relatively high portion of negatively charged phospholipids such as phosphatidylserine. These characteristics might determine the special insertion of certain proteins into mitochondrial membrane (Lutter, Fang et al. 2000).

Figure 3. The mechanisms of mitochondrial membrane permeabilization

One possible model is the formation of a mitochondrial channel called the permeability transition pore complex (PTPC), which consists of several proteins including hexokinase, the voltage-dependent anion channel (VDAC) present on the outer membrane, the inner membrane adenine nucleotide translocator (ANT), and the matrix cyclophilin-D (Marzo, Brenner et al. 1998). VDAC is normally responsible for the transport of metabolites between the cytosol and the mitochondrial intermembrane space (Vander Heiden, Li et al. 2001). Cyclophilin D is a soluble protein and cells contains at least eight different cyclophilins outside of the mitochondria, the specificity of the cyclosporin effect on the PTP has been questioned (Martinou and Green 2001).

Tsujimoto et al. have suggested another model where Bax or Bak interact with VDAC to create complex channels sufficiently large to release cytochrome c to pass through VDAC (Tsujimoto 2002). Another possible model is that Bax and Bak are the only Bcl-2 proteins capable of permeabilizing the outer mitochondrial membrane and multimerization of either Bax or Bak results in pore formation, which is stimulated by Bid and Bad result in the release of cytochrome c and activation of effector caspases (Reed 1997; Wei, Lindsten et al. 2000).

Also many variety of cellular stress such as ceramide, Ca^{2+} , nitric oxide, oxygen radicals, pro-oxidants involved in to opening of PTP in both intact cells and in isolated mitochondria by activation of ANT (Vieira, Haouzi et al. 2000; Machida and Osada 2003).

1.8.2 Apoptosis regulation at the endoplasmic reticulum

The endoplasmic reticulum (ER) is a membranous organelle that plays an important role in the folding, transport, and processing of newly synthesized proteins. Approximately one-third of all cellular proteins are translocated into the lumen of ER (Kaufman 1999). ER stress can be induced by several agents, which block ER to golgi transport, inhibit N-linked glycosylation and disrupt Ca^{2+} stores. ER is an important sensor of cellular stress and it may initiate apoptosis by several distinct mechanisms such as by the unfolded protein response (UPR), Ca^{2+} signalling, ER associated caspase-12 and Bcl-2 family proteins.

The ER stress response is initiated by three types of ER membrane receptors: ATF6, IRE1 (serine/threonine kinase) and PERK (for PKR-like ER protein where PKR is RNA activated protein kinase (Kaufman 1999) (Ferri and Kroemer 2001). Activation of these sensors results in the upregulation of genes such as ER BiP/GRP78 (glucose-regulated proteins) (Bertolotti, Zhang et al. 2000).

Another caspase involved in apoptosis, caspase-12, is localized in the endoplasmic reticulum. Caspase-12 is apparently specifically involved in apoptosis that results from various biochemical stresses to the ER, such as disruption of ER calcium ion distributions. Apoptosis triggered through pathways that do not involve the ER apparently does not result in the activation of caspase-12 (Nakagawa, Zhu et al. 2000). The human genome does not encode a functional caspase-12. Caspase-4 appears to be the human equivalent of mouse caspase-12, whereas human caspase-12 is involved in inflammatory responses (Saleh, Vaillancourt et al. 2004).

The transfer of Ca^{2+} from the ER to the mitochondria is required for initiation of programmed cell death by some, but not all, apoptotic signals. The Ca^{2+} content of the

Figure 4. ER response to apoptotic stimuli

ER determines the ability of cells to die. Bax and Bak are key molecules in the triggering and mediation of ER stress-induced apoptosis and also involved in maintaining the Ca²⁺ homeostasis (Wei, Zong et al. 2001). Ca²⁺ in the ER is regulated by the uptake through sarcoplasmic/ER Ca²⁺ ATPase (SERCA) and the released via inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP₃) and ryanodine (Ry) receptors (Yoneda, Kihara et al. 2001) (Berridge, Lipp et al. 2000).

1.8.3 The involvement of nucleus in apoptosis

One of the hallmarks of apoptosis is the cleavage of chromosomal DNA. Nuclear DNA is degraded in apoptotic cells following activation of caspases. The first identified caspase substrate in apoptotic cells was the nuclear enzyme PARP (Lazebnik,

Kaufmann et al. 1994) which is cleaved by effector caspases. This cleavage probably occur in order to prevent ATP-depletion during apoptosis (Affar el, Shah et al. 2002).

Some caspases and Ca^{2+} -regulated serine proteases are involved in the DNA fragmentation and chromatin condensation by cleaving lamin and NuMA, proteins which normally maintain the integrity of the nuclear structure (Rao, Perez et al. 1996).

Bax is also translocated to the nuclear membrane during drug-induced apoptosis (Ho, Lee et al. 1999).

Mitochondrial released AIF is translocated into the nucleus and induced caspase-independent chromatin condensation (Susin, Lorenzo et al. 1999). Both DNase I and II are involved in the chromatin condensation (Torrighia, Perani et al. 1998) and DNA fragmentation (Polzar, Peitsch et al. 1993).

Procaspase-2 found in the nucleus (Zhivotovsky, Samali et al. 1999) and p53 may serve as a link to the stress-induced direct activation of caspase-2 (Paroni et al., 2002).

DNA damage can recognized by DNA-PK (DNA-dependent protein kinase), ATM, and ATR (Durocher and Jackson 2001; Shiloh 2001). p53 is activated by phosphorylation of ATM, DNA-PK and ATR in response to DNA-damage. Activated p53 induces the transcription of many genes, which are involved in DNA damage-induced apoptosis (Vousden 2002).

1.9 LYSOSOMAL INVOLVEMENT IN APOPTOSIS

Lysosomes

Lysosomes (lysosome: from the Greek: lysis; loosen and soma; body) are single membrane bounded organelles found in animal and plant cells. They vary in shape, size and number per cell. Historically lysosomes have been called “suicide bags” and “garbage disposal units”. Lysosomes are one of the organelles that participate in the control of caspase-independent cell death (Foghsgaard, Wissing et al. 2001; Mathiasen and Jaattela 2002).

Lysosomes contain a number of different enzymes including cathepsins, acid phosphatases, DNAases, ribonucleases, glucuronidas and phosphodiesterases. Many of these enzymes have pH optima of about pH 5. Acidic conditions are maintained in the lysosomes by proton pumps (transfer hydrogen ions from the cytosol) in the membrane (Schneider 1979).

Cathepsins

There are 11 human cathepsins with different expression patterns, levels, specificities and different physiological roles. Cathepsins are synthesized as preproenzymes, which are processed during the passage through the endoplasmic reticulum. Procathepsins undergo proteolytic processing to the active, mature enzyme, form in the acidic environment of late endosomes or lysosomes. Cathepsins L and B can be active as both mature and proforms (Kirschke, Wiederanders et al. 1989).

In normal cells, cathepsins are localized in lysosomes and involved in protein degradation and processing. The aspartic protease cathepsin D and the cysteine protease cathepsin B are the most abundant (their lysosomal concentration can be as high as 1 mM). These enzymes are involved in progression of malignant disease as well as in apoptotic cell death. Alterations in their expression, processing and localization have been observed at various levels (Sloane, Herman et al. 1994).

The other abundant lysosomal proteases are the family of papain-like cathepsins related to cathepsin B (cathepsins H, L, K, S, C, X, V, W, F, and O) (Turk, Turk et al. 2000; Turk, Stoka et al. 2002). Cathepsins survive at neutral pH from a few minutes to several hours, allowing transient activity in the cytosol (Kirschke, Wiederanders et al. 1989).

Lysosomes and the control of their stability in the cells are regulated by cystatins (endogenous protein inhibitors) similar to IAP (endogenous inhibitors of caspases) (Turk, Stoka et al. 2002). Cystatins are divided into stefins, cystatins and kininogens. Stefins are intracellular inhibitors, whereas cystatins and kininogens are extracellular as well as thyropins (thyroglobulin type-1 domain inhibitors and the general protease inhibitor 2-macroglobulin. Cystatins inhibit their target enzymes unselectively, whereas thyropins are much more selective (Turk and Bode 1991). Massive lysosomal damage leads to necrosis (Bursch 2001) suggesting that the inhibitory potential of cystatins is exceeded whereas partial lysosomal damage can take control of this and leads to apoptosis (Brunk, Dalen et al. 1997).

The role of cathepsins in the development of cancer

Cathepsin B has broad substrate specificity at both acid and neutral pH (Buck, Karustis et al. 1992) and functions both as an exopeptidase and as an endopeptidase (Keppler, Sameni et al. 1996). Cathepsin B is also involved in proteolytic cascades to activate other proteinases, which in turn mediate extracellular matrix degradation.

Cysteine cathepsins were already shown in the early 1980s to be associated with malignancy. It has later been shown that cathepsins B, H, L are involved in cancer progression either by directly degrading extracellular matrix or by activating other proteases (Koblinski, Ahram et al. 2000). Cathepsins B, L, H and D are highly expressed in various tumours. For example, increased expression and activity of cathepsin B and or cathepsin D have been observed in breast, colorectal, gastric, lung, prostate and thyroid cancers as well as in different brain tumors, including gliomas and meningiomas.

1.9.1 Mechanisms of lysosomal membrane permeabilization

Several mechanisms have been reported to be responsible for lysosomal membrane permeabilization (LMP) and their involvement in the cell death pathways.

Various studies have been documented that the generation of oxidative stress after treatment by TNF- α , lipopolysaccharide and intralysosomal iron-catalysed oxidative processes (Persson, Yu et al. 2003) have been lead to the permeabilization of lysosomes.

It has been shown that activation of phospholipase A2 (PLA2) through hydrogen peroxidase (H₂O₂), TNF- α , oxidative stress and oxidative stress-mediated activation of Ca²⁺ signalling has been resulted degradation of the membrane phospholipids following LMP (Jaattela, Benedict et al. 1995; Zhao, Brunk et al. 2001).

Intracellular sphingosine and A-SMase induced ceramide have also been suggested to be involved in induction of LMP (Kagedal, Zhao et al. 2001; Werneburg, Guicciardi et al. 2002) as well free fatty acids (FFAs) (Finkel and Holbrook 2000) and lysosomotropic agents as well (Ferri and Kroemer 2001).

1.9.2 Lysosomes in the apoptosis pathway

During the 1960s, it has been shown that lysosomal proteases were the first to be involved in apoptosis, but a “lysosomal pathway of apoptosis” has only been recently accepted (Brunk, Neuzil et al. 2001; Ferri and Kroemer 2001; Turk, Stoka et al. 2002; Jaattela and Tschopp 2003). Studies with knockout mice have shown that cathepsin B is a potent inducer of apoptosis (Ferri and Kroemer, 2001, Guicciardi 2000). Cathepsin C was also showed to be involved in the activation of granzyme B (cytotoxic T cell serine protease) and thus indirectly in the activation of caspases (Pham and Ley 1999). However, when Bax^{-/-}Bak^{-/-} MEF cells were treated with granzyme B, apoptosis was induced without cytochrome c release, indicating the existence of a mitochondria-independent cell death.

The release of cathepsins has been recognized as an early initiating event, which results in mitochondrial membrane permeabilization. Cathepsins B, L, D have been associated with mitochondrial dysfunction and caspase- or AIF-mediated apoptosis (in response to various stress stimuli (Brunk and Svensson 1999; Foghsgaard, Wissing et al. 2001; Kagedal, Johansson et al. 2001; Roberg, Kagedal et al. 2002; Bidere, Lorenzo et al. 2003; Boya, Andreau et al. 2003).

The free form of iron within lysosomes has been also reported that may be an important role in the oxidative-dependent cell damage, including apoptosis and necrosis (Brunk, Neuzil et al. 2001). Sphingosine can cause a partial or a total rupture of lysosomes in a dose dependent manner, which can lead to either apoptosis or necrosis (Guicciardi, Deussing et al. 2000; Kagedal, Zhao et al. 2001).

Cathepsins can cleave and activate Bid (Cirman, Oresic et al. 2004) that has a role as one link associated with lysosomal leakage to mitochondrial membrane permeabilization and suggested that cathepsins can induce caspase-dependent apoptosis through tBid (Boya, Andreau et al. 2003; Cirman, Oresic et al. 2004) as well as in a

Bid- and Bcl-2-independent manner. Cathepsins have also been involved in caspase-independent apoptosis through apoptosis-like morphology (Foghsgaard, Wissing et al. 2001).

Several studies using various pharmacological protease inhibitors suggest that cysteine or serine proteases are involved in p53-mediated cell death and p53 triggers an early lysosomal leakage that precedes mitochondrial membrane permeabilization (Yuan, Li et al. 2002).

Lysosomal pathway is also activated by the TNF- α /TNF-R1 signalling through involvement of factor associated with neutral sphingomyelinase activation (FAN) and it is suggested that FAN is upstream of caspase-8/Bid in a signalling cascade increased with lysosomal permeabilization and cathepsin B releasing (Werneburg, Guicciardi et al. 2004).

The ceramide induction in the acidic lysosomal/endosomal compartment has also been suggested to be involved in stress-induced apoptosis (Heinrich, Wickel et al. 1999). An acidic condition in bladder cancer cells results JNK-mediated caspase- and Bcl-2-independent necrosis-like cell death (Zanke, Lee et al. 1998) as well as post-translational modification of an anti-apoptotic serine protease inhibitor lead to nuclear changes as a typical for apoptosis-like cell death (Altairac, Wright et al. 2003).

It has also reported that NF- κ B is suppressed TNF- α -lysosome-mediated apoptosis through inhibition of cathepsin B with Spi2A (serine protease inhibitor 2A) (Liu, Raja et al. 2003), increased expression of endogenous cysteine cathepsin inhibitors (Kuopio, Kankaanranta et al. 1998) and also increased activity of phosphoinositol-3-kinase that protect cells from cathepsins-mediated apoptosis (Madge, Li et al. 2003).

Figure 5. Lysosomes may triggers cell death

2 THE PRESENT STUDY

2.1 AIM(S)

Conventional cancer therapy using cytostatic drugs is hampered by problems of severe side effects and the development of resistance. Despite the widespread use and the clinical efficiency of cytotoxic drugs, the mechanisms of action of these drugs are not well understood.

The aims of this thesis was to study identify agents that induce p53-independent apoptosis and to characterize the mechanisms of action such drugs (paper III and IV) and to develop a new approach for monitor treatment in patients (paper I and II).

2.2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.2.1 Paper I and Paper II

Various methods have been used for characterization of apoptotic cell death, including flow cytometry (Darzynkiewicz, Juan et al. 1997), TUNEL (Gorczyca, Gong et al. 1993), annexin-V (Koopman, Reutelingsperger et al. 1994), caspase activity by PARP cleavage (Lazebnik, Kaufmann et al. 1994) and cytokeratin-18 (CK18) (Leers, Kolgen et al. 1999). These methods are widely used for quantification of apoptosis, but are not appropriate for high-through-put screening for pro-apoptotic agents. Anti-cancer drug screens can be performed by cell-free and cell-based assays. Cell-based assays have the advantage of presenting targets within a relevant cellular context. The M30-Apoptosense assay (Hagg, Biven et al. 2002) is a 96-well ELISA apoptosis assay. The assay uses a monoclonal antibody (M30), which recognizes a neo-epitope on CK18 exposed after cleavage by caspases at Asp396 (Leers, Kolgen et al. 1999).

In study I, we elucidated the potential use of the M30-assay for screening and characterization of compounds that induce apoptosis of tumour cells. The sensitivity of this assay is sufficient for use in the 96-well format. The assay is suitable for high-through-put screening of proapoptotic drugs (Hagg, Biven et al. 2002; Erdal, Berndtsson et al. 2005). The assay is very useful for establishment of time kinetics of apoptosis induction, information, which is important for further drug characterization. One of the drugs examined in study I, WH-28, induced very rapid CK18 cleavage and was later found to have profound effects on mitochondria within 30 minutes. The National Cancer institute has screened more than 60.000 compounds against a panel of 60 human cell lines. The 50 % growth-inhibitory concentration for each cell line is measured using the MTT-assay and reflects cytotoxicity or cytostasis. The pattern of growth inhibition by each compound is like a fingerprint (Monks, Scudiero et al. 1997).

We examined the possibility to use one cell line and a set of inhibitors for profiling instead of a panel of cell lines. We found that a series of related compounds showed very similar inhibition profiles, which were distinct from that of an unrelated compound (camptothecin). Using inhibitors for profiling has the advantage that the mechanistic insights into drug action is achieved. A number of serum markers have long been used for cancer screening and for monitoring of disease. As example of a commonly used serum assay is prostate-specific antigen (PSA) (Duffy 2001). Serum cytokeratins (CKs) have been extensively used as tumour markers for monitoring patients with carcinomas (Stigbrand 2001). TPA (tissue polypeptide antigen) detects cytokeratins 8, 18, and 19 (Weber, Osborn et al. 1984), CYFRA 21-1 detects CK19 (Rastel, Ramaioli et al. 1994) and TPS (tissue-polypeptide-specific antigen) detect A C-terminal epitope on CK18 (Rydlander, Ziegler et al. 1996). A positive association has been described between the levels of TPA in breast cancer cytosols and apoptosis (Gion, Boracchi et al. 2000). Ueno et al. (Ueno, Toi et al. 2003) demonstrated increased levels of caspase-cleaved CK18 (CK18-Asp396) in serum from cancer patients. In study I, we measured CK18-Asp396 fragments in cancer patient sera during cancer treatment. We found that the levels of caspase cleaved CK18 fragment in patients with recurrent breast cancer increased during chemotherapy and this increase correlated with the treatment effect in these patients. This was only true for patients with low initial levels; patients with high levels of circulating CK18 before treatment show no correlation between alterations in CK18-Asp396 fragment and clinical response. One possible explanation for this difference is that treatment-induced CK18 release does not

surpass a high background level. We conclude from this study I that the M30-ELISA can be used for drug screening and can be possibly be used for measuring drug-induced tumour apoptosis in cancer serum.

In our study II, we examined whether we could determine whether tumour cells die by apoptosis or necrosis by analysis of the molecular forms of CK18 that are released from carcinoma cells during cell death. For this purpose we developed another assay, the M65-ELISA. The M65-ELISA assay measures full-length soluble CK18 and CK18 COOH terminal fragments. Human MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells were used for characterization of the mechanisms of CK18 release in vitro. MDA-MB-231 cells were treated with cisplatin for induction apoptosis and with oligomycin for induction of necrosis. Our results show that treatment of cells with oligomycin resulted in about 90 % of the cellular content of soluble CK18 being released into the medium. Only 1 % of the extracellular CK18 was caspase-cleaved. However, after treatment of cells with cisplatin about 85 % of total CK18 that was released from cells was caspase-cleaved. These findings suggest that the relative levels of total and caspase-cleaved CK18 protein in the extracellular compartment reflect differences in cell death modes.

We then examined whether apoptosis or necrosis dominates in tumours in patients. For this purpose we used local venous blood collected from patients with endometrial tumours during operation. By using tumour venous blood we hoped to minimize problem of different halflives of different CK18 forms in circulation. Our results showed large differences in caspase cleaved and total CK18 ratios between different patients, suggesting that circulating CK18 in tumours often is not generated by apoptosis. Monitoring CK18 in patients with prostate cancer before and during chemotherapy showed differences also in the molecular form of released CK18 between patients. In some patients, increases of mainly uncleaved CK18 was observed during therapy, suggesting that apoptosis is not the main mechanisms of therapy associated cell death in the corresponding tumours.

In summary we have developed simple assay system for detection of apoptosis and also necrosis both in vivo and in vitro. These techniques can be applied to clinical material (patient serum) to study the induction of cell death in tumours during treatment. Apoptosis is frequently impaired in human tumours due to mutation of p53, overexpression of Bcl-2 and inhibitors of apoptosis (IAPs). Furthermore, apoptosis is an energy requiring process, and may be impaired in hypoxic tumours. Apoptosis may therefore not be an ideal endpoint. CK18 measurements may an attractive clinical endpoint for evaluation of treatment efficiency.

2.2.2 Paper III and Paper IV

Apoptosis is a major cause of the cytotoxic effects of chemotherapeutic agents and defects in apoptosis signalling pathways may result in multi-drug resistance. Loss of p53 function has been reported to reduce drug-induced apoptosis in vitro (Lowe 1995). Mutations of p53 occur in the majority of human cancers and several clinical correlative studies report an association between wildtype (wt) p53 and drug response indicating that the p53 status may decide clinical response to chemotherapy (Wallace-Brodeur and Lowe 1999). In our study III, this hypothesis motivated us to search for agents that induce p53 independent apoptosis and to characterize the mechanisms of action of such drugs. We screened a drug library from the National Cancer Institute (NCI) (The Mechanistic set, consisting of 879 compounds with distinct growth inhibition patterns in 60 human tumour cell lines).

We found that 175 of these 879 compounds induce apoptosis on HCT116 p53wt and p53mut colon cancer cells at 5 μ M. However, none of these drugs was absolutely dependent on p53 for induction of apoptosis. We selected 20 agents from the set of 175 compounds for further studies. Five of these 20 compounds induced stronger apoptosis in wt p53 cells, DNA damage was induced by 4/5 these agents. This type of result was expected since sensors of DNA damage such as DNA-PK, ATM and ATR transmit signals that lead to the activation of the p53 pathway (Lakin and Jackson 1999). Of the remaining 15 compounds, 11 were found to be capable of activating caspase-3 induced enucleated cytoplasts.

Further study shows that 7 of the agents with a non-nuclear target induced lysosomal membrane permeabilization (LMP). We observed release of cathepsin-B and cathepsin-D from lysosomes into the cytosol after drug treatment found that apoptosis was inhibited by pepstatin A. These findings suggest that cathepsin-D released from the lysosomes is involved in induction of the apoptotic response. Other investigators have previously reported that cathepsins translocate from the lysosomal lumen to the cytosol after treatment with various apoptotic agents (Foghsgaard, Wissing et al. 2001; Guicciardi, Leist et al. 2004; Jaattela, Cande et al. 2004). Genetic and pharmacological studies demonstrate that either cathepsin B or D are rate limiting for death induced by interferon-, tumor necrosis factor-, p53, or pro-oxidants, at least in some cell types (Levy-Strumpf and Kimchi 1998; Foghsgaard, Wissing et al. 2001; Mathiasen and Jaattela 2002). It has also been reported that addition of purified cathepsin B or D to mitochondria in vitro results in substantial ROS generation (Zhao, Antunes et al. 2003) and that isolated mitochondria are incubated with purified cathepsin B in the presence of cytosolic extracts result in release of cytochrome c (Guicciardi, Deussing et al. 2000).

To test the hypothesis that agents that induce LMP induce a mitochondrial apoptotic pathway, we used a HCT116 Bax null cell line (Zhang, Yu et al. 2000). We found that Bax is required for activation of caspases and for apoptosis by all compounds including those that induce LMP. Cathepsin-D has been demonstrated to induce activation of Bax (Bidere, Lorenzo et al. 2003). It has also been documented that cathepsins cleave and activate Bid and suggested that cathepsins can induce caspase-dependent cathepsin mediated apoptosis through tBid (Cirman, Oresic et al. 2004). Caspase cleavage of CK18 was found to decrease with increasing concentrations for 10 compounds, 5 of which belonged to the group of LMP inducing drugs. We found that these drugs trigger an apoptotic response at low concentrations and apoptosis then shifts to necrosis at higher concentrations. Cell death induced by free radicals may have characteristics of

apoptosis or necrosis (Kane, Sarafian et al. 1993) depending on the concentration. Others have been reported that lysosomal breakdown can be partial or selective in the apoptotic pathway (Werneburg, Guicciardi et al. 2002; Madge, Li et al. 2003), whereas a complete lysosomal breakdown may result in concentrations of cathepsins in the cytosol resulting in necrosis (Bursch 2001; Turk, Stoka et al. 2002) (Li W, 2000, Turk et al., 2002, Bursch W, 2001). For example, low concentrations of sphingosine induces partial lysosomal rupture resulting in apoptosis, whereas higher concentrations lead to total lysosomal rupture and necrosis (Kagedal, Zhao et al. 2001).

We conclude from study III that a large number of potential anti-cancer drugs induce p53- independent apoptosis, and that LMP is a mediator of many such responses. Apoptosis was dependent on Bax, suggesting that LMP induced a mitochondrial apoptotic pathway. Many compounds induced necrosis at concentrations at or below 10 μ M and it is possible that induction of necrosis by anti-cancer drugs is more commonly occurring than generally believed. Considering the high frequency of p53 mutations in human cancer cells, our findings raise the question of whether the lysosomal pathway of cell death may represent a potential target for cancer therapy.

In our study IV, we elucidated the mechanisms of LMP induction by our compounds. Several mechanisms have been reported to be responsible for LMP in the literature, including generation of ROS through various stimuli (Devary, Gottlieb et al. 1991; Zhao, Brunk et al. 2001), intracellular sphingosine and ceramide (Heinrich, Wickel et al. 1999; Werneburg, Guicciardi et al. 2002), lysosomotropic agents (Ferri and Kroemer 2001) and free fatty acids (Acosta and Wenzel 1974). Lysosomal rupture has been established as an early response to oxidative stress (Kagedal, Johansson et al. 2001). Interestingly, the lysosomotropic agents, hydroxychloroquine, norfloxacin and ciprofloxacin have been shown to induce mitochondrial membrane transition in response to LMP in a p53-independent manner (Yuan, Li et al. 2002; Boya, Andreau et al. 2003).

We hypothesized that LMP induction may be associated with the generation of ROS. We therefore assessed drug-induced ROS in p53-deficient HCT116 cells. Eight of the compounds in our set of 20 were found to reproducibly induce ROS within 3 hours. Four of these compounds induced LMP. We examined the effects of the ROS scavenger N-acetyl cysteine (NAC) and the iron chelator desferoxamine (DFO). We found that the induction of LMP was inhibited by pre-treatment of cells with NAC. Apoptosis by 2 LMP-inducing compounds was inhibited by NAC. Lysosomal free iron has been reported to be of importance for oxidative dependent cell damage (Brunk, Neuzil et al. 2001). Free iron within lysosomes can together with H_2O_2 participate in Fenton-type reactions that generate extremely reactive hydroxyl radicals. DFO can chelate free lysosomal iron and protect lysosomes from H_2O_2 (Brunk, Neuzil et al. 2001). Apoptosis induced by one compound that was found to be inhibited by DFO, suggesting a role of lysosomal iron.

Bax is found mainly in the cytosol and localizes to mitochondria and the ER in response to death stimuli (Nechushtan, Smith et al. 1999). Oligomerized Bax can form channels in planar lipid bilayers (Reed 1997). Interestingly, Feldstein et al. have reported that free fatty acid (FFA) treatment of liver cells leads to translocation of Bax from the cytosol to lysosomes and permeabilization of lysosomes followed by release of cathepsin B (Feldstein, Werneburg et al. 2004). We found that 3 drugs did not induce LMP or mitochondrial permeability transition (MPT) in Baxnull cells. Opening of high

conductance permeability transition pores in mitochondria initiates onset of the MPT. The mechanism behind the mitochondrial membrane permeabilization is not clearly understood and several models have been suggested to explain this effect. Following cellular stress pro-apoptotic proteins of Bcl-2 family can relocate to the surface of the mitochondria where the anti-apoptotic proteins are located. This interaction between pro- and anti-apoptotic proteins disrupts the normal function of the anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 proteins and can lead to the formation of pores in the mitochondria and the release of cytochrome c as well as other pro-apoptotic molecules from the intermembrane space. This in turn leads to the formation of the apoptosome and the activation of the caspase cascade.

Interestingly, these 3 agents did not induce ROS. These 3 agents induced LMP and release of cathepsin D after 2.5 hours in Baxwt HCT116 cells, a time-point when cytochrome c release was not detected. LMP is therefore the primary event, followed by triggering of a mitochondrial apoptosis pathway. A possible mechanism for Bax-dependent LMP would be that Bax translocates to the lysosomal membrane after apoptotic stimuli, leading to the formation of pores with a mechanism similar to observed in the outer mitochondrial membrane

We found that apoptosis by one LMP-inducing compound was inhibited by about 30-40 % by the caspase-8 inhibitor z-IETD-fmk. Extrinsic apoptotic cell death is receptor-linked and initiates apoptosis by activating caspase-8. It is possible that receptor-linked apoptosis pathway is involved in apoptosis-induction by this agent.

It has been reported that one of the drugs in our study, Helenalin, triggers apoptosis by a mitochondrial pathway that is insensitive to overexpressing of Bcl-xL and Bcl-2 (Dirsch, Stuppner et al. 2001). Insensitivity to Bcl-2/Bcl-xL was observed at high drug concentrations (20 and 50 μ M), concentrations that induce necrosis and not apoptosis in our hands (paper III, fig.2). It has also been reported that Helenalin inhibits NF- κ B activation in response to different stimuli (Lyss, Schmidt et al. 1997).

In summary we found that ROS was associated with induction of LMP and apoptosis by 4 of 7 LMP-inducing compounds, but not by the remaining 3/7 LMP-inducing agents. A regulated LMP mechanism detected that Bax requires for induction of LMP. Our results suggest that a Bax-regulated pathway of LMP induction exists. These compounds act either directly or indirectly to induce Bax oligomerization and in turn translocation of Bax to the lysosomes leading to membrane permeabilization. Bax is known to undergo conformational changes prior to become inserted into the nuclear membrane (Nechushtan, Smith et al. 1999). It would be interesting to examine whether our drugs that induce Bax-dependent apoptosis induce a conformational change of Bax prior to insertion into the lysosome membrane. Other possible explanation may be these drugs activate extracellular signal pathways by agonistic manner through sphingolipid or their metabolites and trigger a series of phosphorylation steps by activation of MAPK, which lead to activation of Bax during this step.

Lysosomes function as death signal integrators, involved in both apoptosis and necrosis. Based on main stages in the formation of a malignant tumour, it seems to be cathepsins play two opposing roles as an executioner of cell death in cytotoxic signalling cascades and as a mediator of tumor invasion. Enhancing the lysosomal cell death pathway may be a therapeutic strategy to overcome the chemoresistance. Further, ROS are also involved in both the initiation and progression of cancer as well as

mediating the apoptotic process. An increased ROS stress in cancer cells may provide a biochemical basis for developing novel therapeutic strategies that exploit these characteristics by further increase oxidative stress may bypass resistance to conventional chemotherapy agents. Due to the high frequency of p53 mutations in human cancer cells, the demonstration that LMP is potentially a common mechanism of action of p53-independent drugs and the association of ROS with induction of LMP are interesting in terms of future drug development.

Figure 6. The mechanism of LMP by ROS.

Table 1. Summary of biological effects of selected compounds

#	Compound (NSC #)	Compound (name)	Apoptos by p53	Apoptos by Bax	Induction of p53	DNA damage	Cytosolic target	Generation of ROS	induction of LMP	induction of Bax-dep./LMP	Caspase-8 inhibition	Caspase-9 inhibition	Z-Vad inhibition
1	69187	9-methoxy-ellipticine	+	+	++	-	-	-	-	-			
2	93419	Steffimycin	+	+	++	+	-	-	-	-			
3	102811	Formycin A	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-			
4	72961	8-azaadenosine	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-			
5	622627		+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-			
6	106408	Anthracyclin meth.-ether	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-			
7	24818	Podophyllotoxin	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-			
8	24819	β -peltatin A	-	+	++	-	-	-	-	-			
9	166381		-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-			
10	13973	Acridine yellow	-	+	++	-	+	-	-	-			
11	10010		-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-			
12	140377	Arnebin	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-			
13	157389		-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-			
14	313981	Gold Cl-3-ethylphosphine	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
15	285116	Siomycin A	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
16	267461	Nanaomycin	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
17	647889		-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
18	651079		-	+	++	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
19	85236	Helenalin	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
20	687852		-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+

Figure 7. Hypothetical model of Bax-dependent induced LMP.

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4 REFERENCES

- Abraham, R. T. (2001). "Cell cycle checkpoint signaling through the ATM and ATR kinases." *Genes Dev* **15**(17): 2177-96.
- Acosta, D. and D. G. Wenzel (1974). "Injury produced by free fatty acids to lysosomes and mitochondria in cultured heart muscle and endothelial cells." *Atherosclerosis* **20**(3): 417-26.
- Adams, J. M. and S. Cory (2001). "Life-or-death decisions by the Bcl-2 protein family." *Trends Biochem Sci* **26**(1): 61-6.
- Affar el, B., R. G. Shah, et al. (2002). "Role of poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase in rapid intracellular acidification induced by alkylating DNA damage." *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **99**(1): 245-50.
- Altairac, S., S. C. Wright, et al. (2003). "L-DNase II activation by the 24 kDa apoptotic protease (AP24) in TNFalpha-induced apoptosis." *Cell Death Differ* **10**(9): 1109-11.
- Atkinson, E. A., M. Barry, et al. (1998). "Cytotoxic T lymphocyte-assisted suicide. Caspase 3 activation is primarily the result of the direct action of granzyme B." *J Biol Chem* **273**(33): 21261-6.
- Berridge, M. J., P. Lipp, et al. (2000). "Signal transduction. The calcium entry pas de deux." *Science* **287**(5458): 1604-5.
- Bertolotti, A., Y. Zhang, et al. (2000). "Dynamic interaction of BiP and ER stress transducers in the unfolded-protein response." *Nat Cell Biol* **2**(6): 326-32.
- Bidere, N., H. K. Lorenzo, et al. (2003). "Cathepsin D triggers Bax activation, resulting in selective apoptosis-inducing factor (AIF) relocation in T lymphocytes entering the early commitment phase to apoptosis." *J Biol Chem* **278**(33): 31401-11.
- Borner, C. and L. Monney (1999). "Apoptosis without caspases: an inefficient molecular guillotine?" *Cell Death Differ* **6**(6): 497-507.
- Boya, P., K. Andreau, et al. (2003). "Lysosomal membrane permeabilization induces cell death in a mitochondrion-dependent fashion." *J Exp Med* **197**(10): 1323-34.
- Brunk, U. T., H. Dalen, et al. (1997). "Photo-oxidative disruption of lysosomal membranes causes apoptosis of cultured human fibroblasts." *Free Radic Biol Med* **23**(4): 616-26.
- Brunk, U. T., J. Neuzil, et al. (2001). "Lysosomal involvement in apoptosis." *Redox Rep* **6**(2): 91-7.
- Brunk, U. T. and I. Svensson (1999). "Oxidative stress, growth factor starvation and Fas activation may all cause apoptosis through lysosomal leak." *Redox Rep* **4**(1-2): 3-11.
- Buck, M. R., D. G. Karustis, et al. (1992). "Degradation of extracellular-matrix proteins by human cathepsin B from normal and tumour tissues." *Biochem J* **282** (Pt 1): 273-8.
- Budihardjo, I., H. Oliver, et al. (1999). "Biochemical pathways of caspase activation during apoptosis." *Annu Rev Cell Dev Biol* **15**: 269-90.
- Bursch, W. (2001). "The autophagosomal-lysosomal compartment in programmed cell death." *Cell Death Differ* **8**(6): 569-81.
- Cheng, E. H., M. C. Wei, et al. (2001). "BCL-2, BCL-X(L) sequester BH3 domain-only molecules preventing BAX- and BAK-mediated mitochondrial apoptosis." *Mol Cell* **8**(3): 705-11.
- Cirman, T., K. Oresic, et al. (2004). "Selective disruption of lysosomes in HeLa cells triggers apoptosis mediated by cleavage of Bid by multiple papain-like lysosomal cathepsins." *J Biol Chem* **279**(5): 3578-87.
- Cocco, R. E. and D. S. Ucker (2001). "Distinct modes of macrophage recognition for apoptotic and necrotic cells are not specified exclusively by phosphatidylserine exposure." *Mol Biol Cell* **12**(4): 919-30.
- Coultas, L., M. Pellegrini, et al. (2003). "Bfk: a novel weakly proapoptotic member of the Bcl-2 protein family with a BH3 and a BH2 region." *Cell Death Differ* **10**(2): 185-92.

- Darzynkiewicz, Z., G. Juan, et al. (1997). "Cytometry in cell necrobiology: analysis of apoptosis and accidental cell death (necrosis)." Cytometry **27**(1): 1-20.
- Davies, K. J. (1999). "The broad spectrum of responses to oxidants in proliferating cells: a new paradigm for oxidative stress." IUBMB Life **48**(1): 41-7.
- Davis, R. J. (2000). "Signal transduction by the JNK group of MAP kinases." Cell **103**(2): 239-52.
- De Zutter, G. S. and R. J. Davis (2001). "Pro-apoptotic gene expression mediated by the p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase signal transduction pathway." Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A **98**(11): 6168-73.
- Desagher, S. and J. C. Martinou (2000). "Mitochondria as the central control point of apoptosis." Trends Cell Biol **10**(9): 369-77.
- Devary, Y., R. A. Gottlieb, et al. (1991). "Rapid and preferential activation of the c-jun gene during the mammalian UV response." Mol Cell Biol **11**(5): 2804-11.
- Dirsch, V. M., H. Stuppner, et al. (2001). "Helenalin triggers a CD95 death receptor-independent apoptosis that is not affected by overexpression of Bcl-x(L) or Bcl-2." Cancer Res **61**(15): 5817-23.
- Du, C., M. Fang, et al. (2000). "Smac, a mitochondrial protein that promotes cytochrome c-dependent caspase activation by eliminating IAP inhibition." Cell **102**(1): 33-42.
- Duffy, M. J. (2001). "Clinical uses of tumor markers: a critical review." Crit Rev Clin Lab Sci **38**(3): 225-62.
- Durocher, D. and S. P. Jackson (2001). "DNA-PK, ATM and ATR as sensors of DNA damage: variations on a theme?" Curr Opin Cell Biol **13**(2): 225-31.
- Eguchi, Y., S. Shimizu, et al. (1997). "Intracellular ATP levels determine cell death fate by apoptosis or necrosis." Cancer Res **57**(10): 1835-40.
- el-Deiry, W. S., S. E. Kern, et al. (1992). "Definition of a consensus binding site for p53." Nat Genet **1**(1): 45-9.
- Ellis, H. M. and H. R. Horvitz (1986). "Genetic control of programmed cell death in the nematode *C. elegans*." Cell **44**(6): 817-29.
- Erdal, H., M. Berndtsson, et al. (2005). "Induction of lysosomal membrane permeabilization by compounds that activate p53-independent apoptosis." Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A **102**(1): 192-7.
- Evan, A. P. and W. G. Dail, Jr. (1974). "The effects of sodium chromate on the proximal tubules of the rat kidney. Fine structural damage and lysozymuria." Lab Invest **30**(6): 704-15.
- Fadeel, B., B. Zhivotovsky, et al. (1999). "All along the watchtower: on the regulation of apoptosis regulators." Faseb J **13**(13): 1647-57.
- Feinendegen, L. E. (2002). "Reactive oxygen species in cell responses to toxic agents." Hum Exp Toxicol **21**(2): 85-90.
- Feldstein, A. E., N. W. Werneburg, et al. (2004). "Free fatty acids promote hepatic lipotoxicity by stimulating TNF- α expression via a lysosomal pathway." Hepatology **40**(1): 185-94.
- Ferri, K. F. and G. Kroemer (2001). "Organelle-specific initiation of cell death pathways." Nat Cell Biol **3**(11): E255-63.
- Finkel, T. and N. J. Holbrook (2000). "Oxidants, oxidative stress and the biology of ageing." Nature **408**(6809): 239-47.
- Foghsgaard, L., D. Wissing, et al. (2001). "Cathepsin B acts as a dominant execution protease in tumor cell apoptosis induced by tumor necrosis factor." J Cell Biol **153**(5): 999-1010.
- Fuchs, E. and K. Weber (1994). "Intermediate filaments: structure, dynamics, function, and disease." Annu Rev Biochem **63**: 345-82.
- Gao, G. and Q. P. Dou (2000). "N-terminal cleavage of bax by calpain generates a potent proapoptotic 18-kDa fragment that promotes bcl-2-independent cytochrome C release and apoptotic cell death." J Cell Biochem **80**(1): 53-72.
- Gion, M., P. Boracchi, et al. (2000). "Quantitative measurement of soluble cytokeratin fragments in tissue cytosol of 599 node negative breast cancer patients: a prognostic marker possibly associated with apoptosis." Breast Cancer Res Treat **59**(3): 211-21.

- Goldstein, J. C., N. J. Waterhouse, et al. (2000). "The coordinate release of cytochrome c during apoptosis is rapid, complete and kinetically invariant." *Nat Cell Biol* **2**(3): 156-62.
- Gorczyca, W., J. Gong, et al. (1993). "Detection of DNA strand breaks in individual apoptotic cells by the in situ terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase and nick translation assays." *Cancer Res* **53**(8): 1945-51.
- Guicciardi, M. E., J. Deussing, et al. (2000). "Cathepsin B contributes to TNF-alpha-mediated hepatocyte apoptosis by promoting mitochondrial release of cytochrome c." *J Clin Invest* **106**(9): 1127-37.
- Guicciardi, M. E., M. Leist, et al. (2004). "Lysosomes in cell death." *Oncogene* **23**(16): 2881-90.
- Gupta, S., D. Campbell, et al. (1995). "Transcription factor ATF2 regulation by the JNK signal transduction pathway." *Science* **267**(5196): 389-93.
- Hagg, M., K. Biven, et al. (2002). "A novel high-through-put assay for screening of pro-apoptotic drugs." *Invest New Drugs* **20**(3): 253-9.
- Halliwell, B. (2000). "A super way to kill cancer cells?" *Nat Med* **6**(10): 1105-6.
- Hannun, Y. A., C. Luberto, et al. (2001). "Enzymes of sphingolipid metabolism: from modular to integrative signaling." *Biochemistry* **40**(16): 4893-903.
- Harris, J. L., B. J. Backes, et al. (2000). "Rapid and general profiling of protease specificity by using combinatorial fluorogenic substrate libraries." *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **97**(14): 7754-9.
- Heinrich, M., M. Wickel, et al. (1999). "Cathepsin D targeted by acid sphingomyelinase-derived ceramide." *Embo J* **18**(19): 5252-63.
- Ho, Y. S., H. M. Lee, et al. (1999). "Induction of Bax protein and degradation of lamin A during p53-dependent apoptosis induced by chemotherapeutic agents in human cancer cell lines." *Biochem Pharmacol* **57**(2): 143-54.
- Hwang, P. M., F. Bunz, et al. (2001). "Ferrodoxin reductase affects p53-dependent, 5-fluorouracil-induced apoptosis in colorectal cancer cells." *Nat Med* **7**(10): 1111-7.
- Igney, F. H. and P. H. Krammer (2002). "Death and anti-death: tumour resistance to apoptosis." *Nat Rev Cancer* **2**(4): 277-88.
- Jaattela, M., M. Benedict, et al. (1995). "Bcl-x and Bcl-2 inhibit TNF and Fas-induced apoptosis and activation of phospholipase A2 in breast carcinoma cells." *Oncogene* **10**(12): 2297-305.
- Jaattela, M., C. Cande, et al. (2004). "Lysosomes and mitochondria in the commitment to apoptosis: a potential role for cathepsin D and AIF." *Cell Death Differ* **11**(2): 135-6.
- Jaattela, M. and J. Tschopp (2003). "Caspase-independent cell death in T lymphocytes." *Nat Immunol* **4**(5): 416-23.
- Jackson, A. L. and L. A. Loeb (2001). "The contribution of endogenous sources of DNA damage to the multiple mutations in cancer." *Mutat Res* **477**(1-2): 7-21.
- Jarvis, W. D., F. A. Fornari, Jr., et al. (1998). "Evidence for involvement of mitogen-activated protein kinase, rather than stress-activated protein kinase, in potentiation of 1-beta-D-arabinofuranosylcytosine-induced apoptosis by interruption of protein kinase C signaling." *Mol Pharmacol* **54**(5): 844-56.
- Kagedal, K., U. Johansson, et al. (2001). "The lysosomal protease cathepsin D mediates apoptosis induced by oxidative stress." *Faseb J* **15**(9): 1592-4.
- Kagedal, K., M. Zhao, et al. (2001). "Sphingosine-induced apoptosis is dependent on lysosomal proteases." *Biochem J* **359**(Pt 2): 335-43.
- Kamata, H. and H. Hirata (1999). "Redox regulation of cellular signalling." *Cell Signal* **11**(1): 1-14.
- Kane, D. J., T. A. Sarafian, et al. (1993). "Bcl-2 inhibition of neural death: decreased generation of reactive oxygen species." *Science* **262**(5137): 1274-7.
- Kaufman, R. J. (1999). "Stress signaling from the lumen of the endoplasmic reticulum: coordination of gene transcriptional and translational controls." *Genes Dev* **13**(10): 1211-33.
- Keppler, D., M. Sameni, et al. (1996). "Tumor progression and angiogenesis: cathepsin B & Co." *Biochem Cell Biol* **74**(6): 799-810.
- Kerr, J. F., A. H. Wyllie, et al. (1972). "Apoptosis: a basic biological phenomenon with wide-ranging implications in tissue kinetics." *Br J Cancer* **26**(4): 239-57.

- Kim, J. S., T. Qian, et al. (2003). "Mitochondrial permeability transition in the switch from necrotic to apoptotic cell death in ischemic rat hepatocytes." Gastroenterology **124**(2): 494-503.
- Kirschke, H., B. Wiederanders, et al. (1989). "Cathepsin S from bovine spleen. Purification, distribution, intracellular localization and action on proteins." Biochem J **264**(2): 467-73.
- Kluck, R. M., M. D. Esposito, et al. (1999). "The pro-apoptotic proteins, Bid and Bax, cause a limited permeabilization of the mitochondrial outer membrane that is enhanced by cytosol." J Cell Biol **147**(4): 809-22.
- Koblinski, J. E., M. Ahram, et al. (2000). "Unraveling the role of proteases in cancer." Clin Chim Acta **291**(2): 113-35.
- Koopman, G., C. P. Reutelingsperger, et al. (1994). "Annexin V for flow cytometric detection of phosphatidylserine expression on B cells undergoing apoptosis." Blood **84**(5): 1415-20.
- Krajewski, S., S. Tanaka, et al. (1993). "Investigation of the subcellular distribution of the bcl-2 oncoprotein: residence in the nuclear envelope, endoplasmic reticulum, and outer mitochondrial membranes." Cancer Res **53**(19): 4701-14.
- Kroemer, G., P. Petit, et al. (1995). "The biochemistry of programmed cell death." Faseb J **9**(13): 1277-87.
- Kuopio, T., A. Kankaanranta, et al. (1998). "Cysteine proteinase inhibitor cystatin A in breast cancer." Cancer Res **58**(3): 432-6.
- Lakin, N. D. and S. P. Jackson (1999). "Regulation of p53 in response to DNA damage." Oncogene **18**(53): 7644-55.
- Lane, D. P. (1992). "Cancer. p53, guardian of the genome." Nature **358**(6381): 15-6.
- Lazebnik, Y. A., S. H. Kaufmann, et al. (1994). "Cleavage of poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase by a proteinase with properties like ICE." Nature **371**(6495): 346-7.
- Lee, V. Y., D. S. McClintock, et al. (2002). "Hypoxia sensitizes cells to nitric oxide-induced apoptosis." J Biol Chem **277**(18): 16067-74.
- Leers, M. P., W. Kolgen, et al. (1999). "Immunocytochemical detection and mapping of a cytokeratin 18 neo-epitope exposed during early apoptosis." J Pathol **187**(5): 567-72.
- Levy-Strumpf, N. and A. Kimchi (1998). "Death associated proteins (DAPs): from gene identification to the analysis of their apoptotic and tumor suppressive functions." Oncogene **17**(25): 3331-40.
- Li, L. Y., X. Luo, et al. (2001). "Endonuclease G is an apoptotic DNase when released from mitochondria." Nature **412**(6842): 95-9.
- Lin, Y., S. Choksi, et al. (2004). "Tumor necrosis factor-induced nonapoptotic cell death requires receptor-interacting protein-mediated cellular reactive oxygen species accumulation." J Biol Chem **279**(11): 10822-8.
- Lithgow, T., R. van Driel, et al. (1994). "The protein product of the oncogene bcl-2 is a component of the nuclear envelope, the endoplasmic reticulum, and the outer mitochondrial membrane." Cell Growth Differ **5**(4): 411-7.
- Liu, N., S. M. Raja, et al. (2003). "NF-kappaB protects from the lysosomal pathway of cell death." Embo J **22**(19): 5313-22.
- Lockshin, R. A. and C. M. Williams (1965). "Programmed cell death. IV. The influence of drugs on the breakdown of the intersegmental muscles of silkworms." J Insect Physiol **11**(6): 803-9.
- Lockshin, R. A. and C. M. Williams (1965). "Programmed cell death. V. Cytolytic enzymes in relation to the breakdown of the intersegmental muscles of silkworms." J Insect Physiol **11**(7): 831-44.
- Lowe, S. W. (1995). "Cancer therapy and p53." Curr Opin Oncol **7**(6): 547-53.
- Luo, X., I. Budihardjo, et al. (1998). "Bid, a Bcl2 interacting protein, mediates cytochrome c release from mitochondria in response to activation of cell surface death receptors." Cell **94**(4): 481-90.
- Lutter, M., M. Fang, et al. (2000). "Cardiolipin provides specificity for targeting of tBid to mitochondria." Nat Cell Biol **2**(10): 754-61.
- Lyss, G., T. J. Schmidt, et al. (1997). "Helenalin, an anti-inflammatory sesquiterpene lactone from Arnica, selectively inhibits transcription factor NF-kappaB." Biol Chem **378**(9): 951-61.

- Machida, K. and H. Osada (2003). "Molecular interaction between cyclophilin D and adenine nucleotide translocase in cytochrome c release: does it determine whether cytochrome c release is dependent on permeability transition or not?" Ann N Y Acad Sci **1010**: 182-5.
- MacLachlan, T. K. and W. S. El-Deiry (2002). "Apoptotic threshold is lowered by p53 transactivation of caspase-6." Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A **99**(14): 9492-7.
- Madge, L. A., J. H. Li, et al. (2003). "Inhibition of phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase sensitizes vascular endothelial cells to cytokine-initiated cathepsin-dependent apoptosis." J Biol Chem **278**(23): 21295-306.
- Mandic, A., K. Viktorsson, et al. (2002). "Calpain-mediated Bid cleavage and calpain-independent Bak modulation: two separate pathways in cisplatin-induced apoptosis." Mol Cell Biol **22**(9): 3003-13.
- Marchenko, N. D., A. Zaika, et al. (2000). "Death signal-induced localization of p53 protein to mitochondria. A potential role in apoptotic signaling." J Biol Chem **275**(21): 16202-12.
- Martinou, J. C. and D. R. Green (2001). "Breaking the mitochondrial barrier." Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol **2**(1): 63-7.
- Martins, L. M., I. Iaccarino, et al. (2002). "The serine protease Omi/HtrA2 regulates apoptosis by binding XIAP through a reaper-like motif." J Biol Chem **277**(1): 439-44.
- Marzo, I., C. Brenner, et al. (1998). "The permeability transition pore complex: a target for apoptosis regulation by caspases and bcl-2-related proteins." J Exp Med **187**(8): 1261-71.
- Mathias, S., L. A. Pena, et al. (1998). "Signal transduction of stress via ceramide." Biochem J **335 (Pt 3)**: 465-80.
- Mathiasen, I. S. and M. Jaattela (2002). "Triggering caspase-independent cell death to combat cancer." Trends Mol Med **8**(5): 212-20.
- Melino, G., V. De Laurenzi, et al. (2002). "p73: Friend or foe in tumorigenesis." Nat Rev Cancer **2**(8): 605-15.
- Miyashita, T. and J. C. Reed (1995). "Tumor suppressor p53 is a direct transcriptional activator of the human bax gene." Cell **80**(2): 293-9.
- Moldovan, L., K. Irani, et al. (1999). "The actin cytoskeleton reorganization induced by Rac1 requires the production of superoxide." Antioxid Redox Signal **1**(1): 29-43.
- Monks, A., D. A. Scudiero, et al. (1997). "The NCI anti-cancer drug screen: a smart screen to identify effectors of novel targets." Anticancer Drug Des **12**(7): 533-41.
- Muchmore, S. W., M. Sattler, et al. (1996). "X-ray and NMR structure of human Bcl-xL, an inhibitor of programmed cell death." Nature **381**(6580): 335-41.
- Nakagawa, T., H. Zhu, et al. (2000). "Caspase-12 mediates endoplasmic-reticulum-specific apoptosis and cytotoxicity by amyloid-beta." Nature **403**(6765): 98-103.
- Nakano, K. and K. H. Vousden (2001). "PUMA, a novel proapoptotic gene, is induced by p53." Mol Cell **7**(3): 683-94.
- Nechushtan, A., C. L. Smith, et al. (1999). "Conformation of the Bax C-terminus regulates subcellular location and cell death." Embo J **18**(9): 2330-41.
- Nicholson, D. W. and N. A. Thornberry (1997). "Caspases: killer proteases." Trends Biochem Sci **22**(8): 299-306.
- Nilsson, E., R. Ghassemifar, et al. (1997). "Lysosomal heterogeneity between and within cells with respect to resistance against oxidative stress." Histochem J **29**(11-12): 857-65.
- Oda, E., R. Ohki, et al. (2000). "Noxa, a BH3-only member of the Bcl-2 family and candidate mediator of p53-induced apoptosis." Science **288**(5468): 1053-8.
- Persson, H. L., Z. Yu, et al. (2003). "Prevention of oxidant-induced cell death by lysosomotropic iron chelators." Free Radic Biol Med **34**(10): 1295-305.
- Pham, C. T. and T. J. Ley (1999). "Dipeptidyl peptidase I is required for the processing and activation of granzymes A and B in vivo." Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A **96**(15): 8627-32.

- Polzar, B., M. C. Peitsch, et al. (1993). "Overexpression of deoxyribonuclease I (DNase I) transfected into COS-cells: its distribution during apoptotic cell death." Eur J Cell Biol **62**(2): 397-405.
- Puthalakath, H. and A. Strasser (2002). "Keeping killers on a tight leash: transcriptional and post-translational control of the pro-apoptotic activity of BH3-only proteins." Cell Death Differ **9**(5): 505-12.
- Rao, L., D. Perez, et al. (1996). "Lamin proteolysis facilitates nuclear events during apoptosis." J Cell Biol **135**(6 Pt 1): 1441-55.
- Rastel, D., A. Ramaioli, et al. (1994). "CYFRA 21-1, a sensitive and specific new tumour marker for squamous cell lung cancer. Report of the first European multicentre evaluation. CYFRA 21-1 Multicentre Study Group." Eur J Cancer **30A**(5): 601-6.
- Reed, J. C. (1997). "Cytochrome c: can't live with it--can't live without it." Cell **91**(5): 559-62.
- Roberg, K., K. Kagedal, et al. (2002). "Microinjection of cathepsin d induces caspase-dependent apoptosis in fibroblasts." Am J Pathol **161**(1): 89-96.
- Rozenfeld-Granot, G., J. Krishnamurthy, et al. (2002). "A positive feedback mechanism in the transcriptional activation of Apaf-1 by p53 and the coactivator Zac-1." Oncogene **21**(10): 1469-76.
- Rueckert, R. R. and G. C. Mueller (1960). "Effect of oxygen tension on HeLa cell growth." Cancer Res **20**: 944-9.
- Rydlander, L., E. Ziegler, et al. (1996). "Molecular characterization of a tissue-polypeptide-specific-antigen epitope and its relationship to human cytokeratin 18." Eur J Biochem **241**(2): 309-14.
- Saleh, M., J. P. Vaillancourt, et al. (2004). "Differential modulation of endotoxin responsiveness by human caspase-12 polymorphisms." Nature **429**(6987): 75-9.
- Scaffidi, C., S. Fulda, et al. (1998). "Two CD95 (APO-1/Fas) signaling pathways." Embo J **17**(6): 1675-87.
- Schaeffer, H. J. and M. J. Weber (1999). "Mitogen-activated protein kinases: specific messages from ubiquitous messengers." Mol Cell Biol **19**(4): 2435-44.
- Schafer, F. Q. and G. R. Buettner (2001). "Redox environment of the cell as viewed through the redox state of the glutathione disulfide/glutathione couple." Free Radic Biol Med **30**(11): 1191-212.
- Schneider, D. L. (1979). "The acidification of rat liver lysosomes in vitro: a role for the membranous ATPase as a proton pump." Biochem Biophys Res Commun **87**(2): 559-65.
- Scorrano, L. and S. J. Korsmeyer (2003). "Mechanisms of cytochrome c release by proapoptotic BCL-2 family members." Biochem Biophys Res Commun **304**(3): 437-44.
- Shiloh, Y. (2001). "ATM (ataxia telangiectasia mutated): expanding roles in the DNA damage response and cellular homeostasis." Biochem Soc Trans **29**(Pt 6): 661-6.
- Slee, E. A., M. T. Harte, et al. (1999). "Ordering the cytochrome c-initiated caspase cascade: hierarchical activation of caspases-2, -3, -6, -7, -8, and -10 in a caspase-9-dependent manner." J Cell Biol **144**(2): 281-92.
- Sloane, B. F., C. J. Herman, et al. (1994). "Molecular mechanisms of progression and metastasis of human tumors: a pathology B study section workshop. Working Report from the Division of Research Grants, NIH." Cancer Res **54**(19): 5241-5.
- Stieber, P., H. Dienemann, et al. (1993). "Comparison of cytokeratin fragment 19 (CYFRA 21-1), tissue polypeptide antigen (TPA) and tissue polypeptide specific antigen (TPS) as tumour markers in lung cancer." Eur J Clin Chem Clin Biochem **31**(10): 689-94.
- Stigbrand, T. (2001). "The versatility of cytokeratins as tumor markers." Tumour Biol **22**(1): 1-3.
- Susin, S. A., E. Daugas, et al. (2000). "Two distinct pathways leading to nuclear apoptosis." J Exp Med **192**(4): 571-80.
- Susin, S. A., H. K. Lorenzo, et al. (1999). "Molecular characterization of mitochondrial apoptosis-inducing factor." Nature **397**(6718): 441-6.

- Thornberry, N. A. and Y. Lazebnik (1998). "Caspases: enemies within." Science **281**(5381): 1312-6.
- Torriglia, A., P. Perani, et al. (1998). "L-DNase II, a molecule that links proteases and endonucleases in apoptosis, derives from the ubiquitous serpin leukocyte elastase inhibitor." Mol Cell Biol **18**(6): 3612-9.
- Tournier, C., P. Hess, et al. (2000). "Requirement of JNK for stress-induced activation of the cytochrome c-mediated death pathway." Science **288**(5467): 870-4.
- Toyota, H., N. Yanase, et al. (2003). "Calpain-induced Bax-cleavage product is a more potent inducer of apoptotic cell death than wild-type Bax." Cancer Lett **189**(2): 221-30.
- Troyano, A., C. Fernandez, et al. (2001). "Effect of glutathione depletion on antitumor drug toxicity (apoptosis and necrosis) in U-937 human promonocytic cells. The role of intracellular oxidation." J Biol Chem **276**(50): 47107-15.
- Troyano, A., P. Sancho, et al. (2003). "The selection between apoptosis and necrosis is differentially regulated in hydrogen peroxide-treated and glutathione-depleted human promonocytic cells." Cell Death Differ **10**(8): 889-98.
- Tsujimoto, Y. (2002). "Bcl-2 family of proteins: life-or-death switch in mitochondria." Biosci Rep **22**(1): 47-58.
- Tsujimoto, Y. and S. Shimizu (2000). "Bcl-2 family: life-or-death switch." FEBS Lett **466**(1): 6-10.
- Turk, B., V. Stoka, et al. (2002). "Apoptotic pathways: involvement of lysosomal proteases." Biol Chem **383**(7-8): 1035-44.
- Turk, B., D. Turk, et al. (2000). "Lysosomal cysteine proteases: more than scavengers." Biochim Biophys Acta **1477**(1-2): 98-111.
- Turk, V. and W. Bode (1991). "The cystatins: protein inhibitors of cysteine proteinases." FEBS Lett **285**(2): 213-9.
- Ueno, T., M. Toi, et al. (2003). "Measurement of an apoptotic product in the sera of breast cancer patients." Eur J Cancer **39**(6): 769-74.
- van der Vlies, D., J. Woudenberg, et al. (2003). "Protein oxidation in aging: endoplasmic reticulum as a target." Amino Acids **25**(3-4): 397-407.
- Vander Heiden, M. G., X. X. Li, et al. (2001). "Bcl-xL promotes the open configuration of the voltage-dependent anion channel and metabolite passage through the outer mitochondrial membrane." J Biol Chem **276**(22): 19414-9.
- Verhagen, A. M., P. G. Ekert, et al. (2000). "Identification of DIABLO, a mammalian protein that promotes apoptosis by binding to and antagonizing IAP proteins." Cell **102**(1): 43-53.
- Verheij, M., R. Bose, et al. (1996). "Requirement for ceramide-initiated SAPK/JNK signalling in stress-induced apoptosis." Nature **380**(6569): 75-9.
- Vieira, H. L., D. Haouzi, et al. (2000). "Permeabilization of the mitochondrial inner membrane during apoptosis: impact of the adenine nucleotide translocator." Cell Death Differ **7**(12): 1146-54.
- Vogelstein, B., D. Lane, et al. (2000). "Surfing the p53 network." Nature **408**(6810): 307-10.
- Vousden, K. H. (2002). "Activation of the p53 tumor suppressor protein." Biochim Biophys Acta **1602**(1): 47-59.
- Vousden, K. H. and X. Lu (2002). "Live or let die: the cell's response to p53." Nat Rev Cancer **2**(8): 594-604.
- Wallace-Brodeur, R. R. and S. W. Lowe (1999). "Clinical implications of p53 mutations." Cell Mol Life Sci **55**(1): 64-75.
- Weber, K., M. Osborn, et al. (1984). "Tissue polypeptide antigen (TPA) is related to the non-epidermal keratins 8, 18 and 19 typical of simple and non-squamous epithelia: re-evaluation of a human tumor marker." Embo J **3**(11): 2707-14.
- Wei, M. C., T. Lindsten, et al. (2000). "tBID, a membrane-targeted death ligand, oligomerizes BAK to release cytochrome c." Genes Dev **14**(16): 2060-71.
- Wei, M. C., W. X. Zong, et al. (2001). "Proapoptotic BAX and BAK: a requisite gateway to mitochondrial dysfunction and death." Science **292**(5517): 727-30.
- Werneburg, N., M. E. Guicciardi, et al. (2004). "TNF-alpha-mediated lysosomal permeabilization is FAN and caspase 8/Bid dependent." Am J Physiol Gastrointest Liver Physiol **287**(2): G436-43.

- Werneburg, N. W., M. E. Guicciardi, et al. (2002). "Tumor necrosis factor-alpha-associated lysosomal permeabilization is cathepsin B dependent." Am J Physiol Gastrointest Liver Physiol **283**(4): G947-56.
- Wood, D. E. and E. W. Newcomb (1999). "Caspase-dependent activation of calpain during drug-induced apoptosis." J Biol Chem **274**(12): 8309-15.
- Wyllie, A. H. (1985). "The biology of cell death in tumours." Anticancer Res **5**(1): 131-6.
- Wyllie, A. H., J. F. Kerr, et al. (1980). "Cell death: the significance of apoptosis." Int Rev Cytol **68**: 251-306.
- Yoneda, T., Y. Kihara, et al. (2001). "Calcium handling and sarcoplasmic-reticular protein functions during heart-failure transition in ventricular myocardium from rats with hypertension." Life Sci **70**(2): 143-57.
- Yuan, X. M., W. Li, et al. (2002). "Lysosomal destabilization in p53-induced apoptosis." Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A **99**(9): 6286-91.
- Zanke, B. W., C. Lee, et al. (1998). "Death of tumor cells after intracellular acidification is dependent on stress-activated protein kinases (SAPK/JNK) pathway activation and cannot be inhibited by Bcl-2 expression or interleukin 1beta-converting enzyme inhibition." Cancer Res **58**(13): 2801-8.
- Zha, J., H. Harada, et al. (1996). "Serine phosphorylation of death agonist BAD in response to survival factor results in binding to 14-3-3 not BCL-X(L)." Cell **87**(4): 619-28.
- Zha, J., S. Weiler, et al. (2000). "Posttranslational N-myristoylation of BID as a molecular switch for targeting mitochondria and apoptosis." Science **290**(5497): 1761-5.
- Zhang, L., J. Yu, et al. (2000). "Role of BAX in the apoptotic response to anticancer agents." Science **290**(5493): 989-92.
- Zhao, M., F. Antunes, et al. (2003). "Lysosomal enzymes promote mitochondrial oxidant production, cytochrome c release and apoptosis." Eur J Biochem **270**(18): 3778-86.
- Zhao, M., U. T. Brunk, et al. (2001). "Delayed oxidant-induced cell death involves activation of phospholipase A2." FEBS Lett **509**(3): 399-404.
- Zhivotovsky, B., A. Samali, et al. (1999). "Caspases: their intracellular localization and translocation during apoptosis." Cell Death Differ **6**(7): 644-51.
- Zong, W. X., T. Lindsten, et al. (2001). "BH3-only proteins that bind pro-survival Bcl-2 family members fail to induce apoptosis in the absence of Bax and Bak." Genes Dev **15**(12): 1481-6.